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**High Accuracy Measurement Device For
Railways Applications**

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INDEX

Preface	3
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCING THE METROLOGY FOR SMART ENERGY MANAGEMENT IN ELECTRIC RAILWAY SYSTEMS	5
1.1 Characteristics of railway electrical systems	6
1.2 My Rails	9
1.2 Global Position System and Pulse Per Second (GPS and PPS).....	14
CHAPTER 2: SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE AND INSTRUMENTATION FOR MEASUREMENT DEVICE	17
2.1 Measurement device architecture.....	18
2.2 System Architecture	18
2.3 Compact Rio 9082.....	19
2.4 Compact Rio 9034.....	23
2.5 NI C Series Modules Overview	26
2.5.1 NI 9467 GPS Timestamping and Synchronization Module.....	27
2.5.2 NI 9225	27
2.5.3 NI 9227	30
2.5.4 NI 9239	33
2.6 FLUKE 6135A / PMU CAL.....	36
2.7 Fluke 6105A.....	37
2.8 PXI Chassis with NI 5422 and NI 6683H modules	45
CHAPTER 3: DEVELOPED ALGORITHMS AND SOFTWARE IMPLEMENTATION.....	47
3.1 General overview on the implemented algorithms	48
3.2 Synchronization technique	49

3.3	Labview implementation on FPGA	51
3.4	Labview implementation on Controller module	56
3.5	Interpolation in time domain.....	66
3.6	Discrete Fourier transform (DFT).....	69
3.7	Data Processing function.....	74
3.8	Measurements for Power Systems	79
3.9	Labview software for Synchrophasors Measurement	84
CHAPTER 4: VALIDATION AND VERIFICATION OF THE PERFORMANCE OF THE MEASUREMENT DEVICE.....		86
4.1	Validation Test Performed.....	87
4.2	Verification of the synchronization with UTC.....	88
4.3	The efficacy of resampling.....	89
4.4	Performance verification.....	91
4.5	Verification of the reliability of the system	119
Conclusions.....		121
Refecences		122

Preface

Considering the overall annual energy consumption of the European railway system, about 36.5 TWh, and the ambitious target of reducing CO₂ railway transport emissions to 50% by 2030, it is clear that an efficient use of the energy in the railway system is mandatory. Considering also the recent European directives [1–3] that regulate railway networks in European Union (EU) law and allow open access operations on railway lines by companies other than those that own the rail infrastructure, accurate and reliable knowledge of the absorbed/exchanged energy between the train and the railway grid is essential. All the trains shall be equipped with an Energy Measurement Function (EMF), whose measurement accuracy has to be assessed and periodically re-verified. Moreover, an accurate knowledge of the real-time power quality (PQ) is a valuable tool to foster the efficiency of the whole railway system by awarding the good power quality delivered and absorbed. The voltages supplied to trains are often distorted harmonically and subject to residual ripple from alternating current (AC) to direct current (DC) conversion; these distortions are typically much larger than those experienced on the usual electricity network. At the same time, the currents drawn by trains also contain high levels of harmonics, inter-harmonics, ripple and step changes in magnitude associated with train acceleration and braking. Arcing phenomena, generated by a bad pantograph-to-line contact quality, can further introduce transient distortions. Furthermore, the switching frequencies associated with IGBT train drives can resonate causing serious over-voltages, particularly in overhead line (catenary) systems.

The combination of these effects means that accurate determination of real-time power consumption and cumulative energy (and efficiency) metering are significant challenges. Measurement systems and algorithms related to PQ in fixed installations (AC transmission/distribution grids) are currently available; however, these techniques are not all directly applicable to railways, because the time frames of interest are different, the trains are mobile and the PQ phenomena are different. Meanwhile, the existing wide-area measurements on railways are limited to energy consumption with a 300 second (5 minute) time quantization [4]. This provides enough information for particular train operating companies to be billed for energy use, but it provides very little useful data in terms of network management, efficiency assessment, condition

monitoring, power quality and network stability. Moreover, PQ definitions for DC railway distribution systems are still an open research topic.

With respect to energy measurement on-board trains, the current European standard [3] gives requirements for current/voltage sensors and energy calculation function. In several parts, it adopts the requirement given for energy measurement for fixed installation working at 50 Hz. This is a crucial point if we consider the dynamic effects (eg: catenary-pantograph contact) of a railway supply system. To improve the energy measuring systems more bandwidth is needed in order to analyze the described higher frequency phenomena.

All this let us perceive the necessity of a high performance measurement system, that have to collect and analyze railway typical quantities both onboard train and in substation. In order to do this, the first requirement of the system is the sampling synchronization of all the measurement devices to a common time reference. Therefore in this paper an embedded standalone measurement device, that can acquire various types of railway quantities (electrical and mechanical) synchronously to an absolute time reference, obtained by Global Positioning System (GPS) is presented. The proposed instrument has been conceived with flexibility in mind to be used for both substations and trains. It could be used to measure power and energy, to identify the PQ events affecting the power exchanged between the supply system and the rolling stock and to have input information to train eco-driving procedure implementation.

**CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCING THE
METROLOGY FOR SMART
ENERGY MANAGEMENT IN
ELECTRIC RAILWAY SYSTEMS**

1.1 Characteristics of railway electrical systems

The aim of this thesis is to develop a high accuracy and flexible measurement device for voltage and current signals of railway systems in specified instant of time. In this way is possible to monitor the grid state and to analyse the energy flow direction between substations and trains in absolute instants of time. In fact it is possible for the trains return energy during the braking phase. As will be discussed in paragraph 1.2, there is still no legislation that provides an accurate algorithm for measuring energy in the railway sector, so a flexible measuring instrument is needed on which it is possible to easily implement new algorithms for the measurement of power and energy. Therefore, in this paragraph, a brief discussion of the electrical characteristics of European railways is made to understand their characteristics. One of the main problems in the implementation of this project lies in supplying rail lines as shown on the map this is also present in the same country.

Figure 1.1 Map of the electrification systems of the main rail network connections in Europe

For the High Speed / High Capacity line, predominantly 25 k V are used with a 50 Hz and alternating current except for Germany, Austria, Switzerland using the 15 k V - as for the traditional line - but at a frequency of 16 and 2/3. In either case, however, the highest qualitative standards that have been sought (peak train speeds, greatly reduced travel time ...) are guaranteed

TGV

Eurostar

ICE

To understand the principles of modern traction power control systems, it is worth a look at the basics of DC and AC circuitry. DC is direct current, it travels in one direction only along a conductor. AC is alternating current so called because it changes direction, flowing first one way along the conductor, then the other. It does this very rapidly. The number of times it changes direction per second is called the frequency and is measured in Hertz (Hz). It used to be called cycles per second, in case you've read of this in historical papers. In a diagrammatic representation, the two types of current appear as shown in the following diagrams

Figure 1.2: AC current

Figure 1.3: DC current

From a transmission point of view, AC is better than DC because it can be distributed at high voltages over a small size conductor wire, whereas DC needs a large, heavy wire or, on many DC railways, an extra rail. DC also needs more frequent feeder

substations than AC the ratio for a railway averages at about 8 to 1. It varies widely from one application to another but this gives a rough idea.

Over the hundred years or so since the introduction of electric traction on railways, the rule has generally been that AC is used for longer distances and main lines and DC for shorter, suburban or metro lines. DC gets up to 3000 V, while AC uses 15 - 50 V.

Until recently, DC motors have been the preferred type for railways because their characteristics were just right for the job. They were easy to control too. For this reason, even trains powered from AC supplies were usually equipped with DC motors.

Currently, being fully abandoned by the three-phase alternating current system requiring very expensive power lines and complicating locomotion regulation, power supply systems applied to the electric traction rail are virtually limited to DC, single-phase alternating current at the frequency of 'rail' of $16\frac{2}{3}$ Hz and the single-phase alternating current at the industrial frequency of 50 Hz. In DC systems, the supply line voltage is normally 3000 V, but experiments are also being carried out at 6000 V: electricity is drawn from a high-voltage three-phase alternating current line and converted to direct current at the desired voltage in appropriate supply substations. In the single-phase AC system with a frequency of $16\frac{2}{3}$, we need a frequency conversion plant that reduces by 1/3 the frequency of high-voltage alternating current lines to the industrial frequency of 50 Hz. Subsequently, the power substations lower the voltage to the value of 15 k V ordinarily adopted. In the single-phase industrial-frequency alternating current system, there is no longer any need to convert the frequency of high-voltage alternating current lines, the power substations simply lower the voltage to 25 k V or, in some cases, to 50 k V. In Italy, the "Ferrovie dello Stato" and private-sector concession lines are managed by the DC system, which, in the present state of the art, is the most efficient among the examined ones and is referred to throughout the following exposure. In the case examined, the line is 1500 V.

The three-phase high current or high voltage industrial frequency of 50 Hz manufactured at normal power plants is first sent to transformer stations whose task is to reduce the value of the voltage to medium values. From the transformation stations, the three-phase alternating current is sent to the power substations which, by means of

suitable downstream transformers and rectifiers of special characteristics, convert it continuously to the voltage of 3000 V. In Italy the substations are spaced approximately 20 km, but in some sections designed to allow very high speeds, the distance between a substation and the next is reduced to about 16 km. Power substations receive three-phase alternating current from voltage lines between 20 and 150 k V. Upon arrival of these lines are generally installed low-oil type switches with breakdown power between 5000 and 7500 M VA: some have been replaced with switches of similar sulfur hexafluoride type characteristics, which, among other advantages, also eliminate the need for oil filtering, with a sensible benefit to maintenance. Downstream of the protection switches, each substation comprises one or more three-phase transformers equipped with two identical secondary windings that supply one or more solid-state silicon rectifiers, each connected to two bridges connected in parallel (this arrangement is intended to power in future will allow the switch from the DC to 3000 V to 6000 V by simply connecting the two rectifiers bridged in series).

The characteristics of the newly installed transformers are such as to ensure a virtually constant output voltage when also the value of the current absorbed power by the trains along the line supplied line range from a minimum of 75 A to a maximum of 3000 A. I Rectifiers used by “Ferrovie dello stato” are usually equipped with silicon diodes divided into two systems for a total power of 3600 kW: the technological advances of recent years have allowed the use of diodes of the 'type', the use of which, among other things, reduced the size and halved the rectifiers' weights.

1.2 My Rails

The following thesis work is carried out as part of the European research project MYRAILS (coordinated by Domenico Giordano of the national metrological research institute, INRIM) which envisages the "Università degli studi di Napoli Luigi Vanvitelli" University as an internal funded partner. One of the final tasks is to design a wide area architecture for a continuous monitoring of PQ parameters and, at this end, in this thesis work a measurement device for DC and AC railway supply system is shown.

MY RAILS project aims to develop the metrological infrastructure for accurate measurement of energy exchange and for reliable system monitoring, which underpins the implementation of an energy efficient management of the European DC and AC railway and DC subway system. The project also focuses on the characterization of the railway subsystem as a producer-consumer, with a view to its integration in a wide smart grid as well as on the assessment of eco-driving performances.

Considering the overall annual energy consumption of the European railway system, about 36.5 TWh, and the ambitious target of reducing CO₂ railway transport emissions to 50 % by 2030, it is clear that an efficient use of the energy in the railway system is mandatory. To this end, accurate and reliable knowledge of the absorbed/exchanged energy between the train and the railway grid is essential, considering the harsh on-board measurement conditions.

To establish a single European railway area, the European commission requires, by 2019, that the energy billings shall be computed on the actual consumed energy [1],[2]. All the trains shall be equipped with an Energy measurement Function (EMF), whose measurement accuracy has to be assessed and periodically re-verified, as required by [3]. To assess the metrological reliability of the EMF under operating conditions, calibration setups and procedures, which go beyond the well-known procedures developed for pure sinusoidal or continuous regimes, are required.

The efficient use of the infrastructure, encouraged by the European Union, requires new constraints for the railway supply systems. In this scenario, an accurate knowledge of the real-time power quality is a valuable tool to foster the efficiency of the whole railway system by “awarding” the good power quality delivered and absorbed.

New installations of reversible substations in DC railway system, able to transfer the excess of energy, produced during braking to the upstream AC network, can improve energy saving. A reliable procedure in the estimation and measurement of the potential energy saved by Reversible Substations (RSSs) is then a valuable tool in the cost-benefit evaluation. Ecodriving is a further energy saving technique that needs accurate on-board energy measurements for the definition of the best eco-driving strategy. An uncertainty of tens of percent on the absorbed energy makes information useless for the ecodriving efficiency assessment.

The specific objectives of the project are:

1. To develop a metrological framework for calibration (comprising laboratory and on-board train calibration / measurement set-ups and robust data processing algorithms) to enable high accuracy energy and Power Quality (PQ) measurements under highly dynamic electrical conditions approaching the uncertainty limits stated in the EN 50463-2:2013-05. All major European supply systems (25 kV/50 Hz, 15 kV/16.7 Hz, 3 kV/DC, 1.5 kV/DC, 750 V/DC and 600 V/DC) will be considered
2. To develop a wide-area power quality monitoring architecture. This will include diagnostic studies, system models, numerical simulations, power quality indexes definition, measurement system implementation, time-synchronization, wide-area communication, centralized data collection for quantifying the efficient use of the railway infrastructure and for identifying the PQ events affecting the power exchanged between the supply system and the rolling stock (including high-capacity converter devices effects, intermittent sliding-contact arcing and resonance effect).
3. To set up combined measurement-simulation tools to analyse the existing energy-use profiles of DC rolling-stock supplied with traditional unidirectional substations and to quantify the impact of the installation of new Reversible Substation in terms of energy saving but also in terms of Power Quality issues potentially generated
4. To develop accurate measurement systems and procedures for evaluating actual energy saving provided by an ecodriving strategy. The aim is to reduce the uncertainty of the on-board energy measurement up to a few percent to assess the reliability of ecodriving forecasting model and to identify and test good practices in on-site estimation of ecodriving benefit.
5. To facilitate the take up of the technology and measurement infrastructure developed in the project by the measurement supply chain (accredited laboratories), standards developing organizations (EN) and end users (train manufacturers, railway companies).

On the base of EN 50463, which regulates the energy measurement on-board trains, the International Electrotechnical Committee (IEC) Technical Committee (TC) is

introducing new concepts, which enlarge the application of the new standard also for energy management, energy flow estimation and energy saving purposes. For energy measurements on-board trains, the in force European standard [3] adopts the same requirements given for fixed 50 Hz installation, so disregarding wide band effects specific for railway systems. With respect to [1], the present project aims to improve the metrological reliability and decrease the uncertainty of the energy measuring system. To this end, a specific generation setup for calibration purposes, able to generate a phantom power up to 6 MW and superimposed distortions up to 5 kHz will be developed. Under DC supply, the setup will generate 4 MW, with current distortions in a bandwidth up to some kilohertz. The expected accuracy associated with the energy measurement after calibration carried out under distorted conditions, will be 0.5% for the AC regime and 0.1% for the DC one. The uncertainty associated with the knowledge of the generated harmonic/ripple will be of about 0.3% at 5 kHz.

As to the assessment of the power supply quality, [4] defines limit variations for frequency and supply voltage. Monitoring is required only at commissioning or on response of problems. Standard [5] deals with the quality interface between traction unit and fixed installation, it defines the procedure of compatibility assessment (by simulation, test in the lab and on test tracks) only for new rolling stock or new infrastructure component. Significant research on definitions, measurement systems and algorithms related to PQ in fixed installations (AC transmission/distribution grids) has been carried out in the last 10 years. However, techniques are not all directly applicable to railways, because the timeframes of interest are different, the trains are mobile, and the power quality phenomena are different. The project will develop means, methods and a specific metrics for continuous PQ event detection AC and DC supply systems.

Typically, up to 50% of the traction energy is dissipated in braking process, but only 10%-30% is sent back to the catenary, due to the receptivity of the supply network limited by unidirectional nature of the substations. Nowadays, new RSSs, which adopt high voltage high power inverters, allow the bidirectional energy exchange between AC and DC railway grids, saving a traction energy from 11 % to 20 %. Future goal is to enlarge RSS technology from metros and suburban lines to all DC railways. The

high cost of the initial investment requires an accurate estimate of the energy saved by the RSS, up to now carried out only in an indirect way with low accuracy.

Little information is present in literature on the effect of new RSSs on the upstream AC grid. Because of the potential weakness of the AC network, PQ degradation due to the RSS contribution must be evaluated through synchronized measurement and reliable load flow algorithm involving both DC and AC grids. On this subject, standardization support only includes a technical report [6], providing recommendations for new installations of RSS.

Saving of energy through eco-driving entails the application of combined efficient driving strategies to achieve the required running time minimizing the energy consumption [7]. The reduction of the absorbed energy has been estimated of the order of tens percent, that is with the same order of magnitude as the uncertainty associated with the on-board energy measurement. There is then a need of developing measurement systems, able to reduce the on-site absorbed energy uncertainty up to some percent.

With the aim of establishing a single European railway area, the European commission requires, by 2019, that the energy billings shall be computed on the actual consumed energy. Therefore, all trains shall be equipped with an EMF whose measurement accuracy has to be assessed and periodically re-verified, as required by [3].

The voltages supplied to trains are often distorted harmonically and subject to ripple; these distortions are much larger than those experienced on the usual electricity network. At the same time, the currents drawn by trains also contain high levels of harmonics, inter-harmonics, ripple, and step changes in magnitude associated with train acceleration and braking. Arcing phenomena, generated by a bad pantograph-to-line contact quality, can further introduce transient distortions. Furthermore, the switching frequencies associated with IGBT train drives can resonate causing serious-over-voltages, particularly in overhead line (catenary) systems. The combination of these effects means that accurate determination of real-time power consumption, and cumulative energy (and efficiency) metering, are significant challenges.

Getting a clear picture of the energy consumption in a railway network is a difficult task. In many countries, the energy bill is based on a priori assumptions. While the energy efficiency of the trains can be easily predicted, the driving style cannot, even though it is obvious that frequent accelerations and decelerations make the system less efficient than driving at constant speed (eco-driving). Most of the potential improvement for efficiency is linked to operational measures such as eco-driving rather than technical solutions such as more efficient locomotives [8]. Therefore, a significant part of energy efficiency improvements is at present not necessarily translated into a cost reduction for a particular railway company.

1.2 Global Position System and Pulse Per Second (GPS and PPS)

The Navstar Global Positioning System (GPS) is a space-based radionavigation system owned and operated by the United States. GPS has provided positioning, navigation, and timing services to military and civilian users on a continuous worldwide basis since first launch in 1978. An unlimited number of users with a civil or military GPS receiver can determine accurate time and location, in any weather, day or night, anywhere in the world. The United States Air Force, as the Executive Agent for GPS, is responsible for the design, development, procurement, operation, sustainment, and modernization of the system.

The concept of PPS originated with the man's quest in space. The atomic clocks orbiting around the earth in GPS satellites are utilized to obtain accurate timing. Today PPS is found in applications requiring synchronization such as cellular networks, telecommunications timing, digital TV and radio transmission, calibration laboratory systems, internet, stock market, computer games and precision stuff like surveys where various data have to correspond in respect to time. The atomic clocks in the GPS satellites are monitored and compared to 'master clocks' by the GPS Operational Control Segment; this 'GPS time' is steered to within one microsecond of Universal Time.

Figure 1.4: PPS signal

GPS receivers provide 1PPS output signal. This pulse normally has a rising edge aligned with the GPS second, and is used to discipline local clocks to maintain synchronization with Universal Time (UT). Time is crucial in this thesis work because each piece of data received from a device could be stored in the data files, in order to correlate it with data coming from other devices, we need to stamp the time when the measurement was taken.

A computer system's clock speed is measured as a frequency, usually expressed as a number of cycles per second. A crystal oscillator controls clock speeds and its oscillator circuitry is in the motherboard chipset. As voltage is applied to the quartz, it begins to vibrate (oscillate) at a harmonic rate dictated by the shape and size of the crystal (sliver). The oscillations emanate from the crystal in the form of a current that alternates at the harmonic rate of the crystal. This alternating current is the clock signal that forms the time base on which the computer operates. The computer clock is not very precise!

While totally rigorous testing of timing pulses requires an atomic clock reference, useful information can be gathered using a survey-grade, dual-frequency GPS receiver as the timing reference. This sounds relatively straight forward, however, various positioning system manufacturers provide this Time Synchronization timing data in various forms. Time stamps are sent before or after the pulse and the time reference can be the rising or falling flank of the pulse. Some receivers have time offsets between time message and pulse.

Note: While most clocks derive their time from Coordinated Universal Time (UTC), the atomic clocks on the satellites are set to GPS time (GPST). The difference in UTC from GPS time is that GPS time is not corrected to match the rotation of the Earth, so it does not contain leap seconds or other corrections that are periodically added to UTC.

However, GPS navigation message includes the difference between GPS time and UTC. GPS units may not show the correct UTC time until after receiving the UTC offset message. Receivers subtract this offset from GPS time to calculate UTC and specific time zone values. GPS time is theoretically accurate to about 14 nanoseconds.

However, most receivers lose accuracy in the interpretation of the signals and are only accurate to 100 nanoseconds, if not more.

The 1 pps output doesn't come directly from a satellite. It comes from the receivers own internal clock. That clock is synchronized with the satellites. The 1 pps output doesn't go away if the receiver loses reception, it just gets less accurate. This signal could be used as a time reference in data acquisition system for correlating the acquired element with time when it was acquired.

**CHAPTER 2: SYSTEM
ARCHITECTURE AND
INSTRUMENTATION FOR
MEASUREMENT DEVICE**

2.1 Measurement device architecture

The main feature of this thesis project is to realized a flexible instrument that is able to acquire and process different types of signals provided from trains or substations in specified instant of time. To this end, the National Instrument Compact Rio was chosen, which allows the use of different acquisition modules in relation to the type of input signal and a GPS receiver module for relating timing information. The architecture of measurement system expects the following configuration:

Figure 2.1: Measurement device architecture

It is easy to understand that by changing, or adding, acquisition modules downstream of the transducers, it is possible to measure and process any type of physical dimension. Specifically, for this thesis work, the Compact Rio 9082 was used to measure the signals coming from the transducers placed on the train, while for the signals from the transducers located in the substations, two Compact Rio 9034 have been used. The technical specifications of the Compact Rio devices and the modules used are shown in section 2.3

2.2 System Architecture

The Compact Rio 9082 is a stand-alone reconfigurable embedded chassis with integrated real-time controller and thanks to its reduced size, it could be easily positioned on train as well as substations. The system architecture contemplates measurement devices on substations for monitoring and controlling the power flow to the train and another device on the train itself for monitoring dissipated and returned

power. Ad hoc network infrastructure conceived for the interconnection of distributed metering units will be used. Various degrees of interconnection, mobility and autonomy are achieved through the network interfaces, the high-reliability power supply, the real-time configurability and control. A system controller placed in main station could collect data form measurement network and put in relation all the information. In this way, it is possible to monitor operating conditions, power quality, efficiency and network stability.

Figure 2.2: System Architecture

2.3 Compact Rio 9082

Figure 2.3: Compact Rio9082

Powered by the NI LabVIEW reconfigurable I/O (RIO) architecture, NI CompactRIO combines an open embedded architecture with small size, extreme ruggedness, and hot-swappable industrial I/O modules. Each system contains an FPGA for custom timing, triggering, and processing with a wide array of modular I/O to meet any embedded application requirement.

Compact Rio architecture is as follows:

Figure 2.4: Compact Rio Architecture

The following specifications are typical for the -40 °C to 70 °C operating temperature range unless otherwise noted.

Processor

CPU	Intel Core i7-660UE
Number of cores	2
CPU frequency	1.33 GHz (base); 2.4 GHz (single-core Turbo mode)
On-die L2 cache	256 KB x2 (256 KB/core)
On-die L3 cache	4 MB (shared)

Software requirements

Application software

LabVIEW	LabVIEW 2011 or later
	LabVIEW Real-Time Module 2011 or later
	LabVIEW FPGA Module 2011 or later
Driver software	NI CompactRIO Device Drivers 4.0 or later

Internal Real Time Clock

Accuracy	200 ppm; 35 ppm at 25 °C
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Reconfigurable FPGA

FPGA type	Xilinx Spartan-6 LX 150
Number of flip flops	184,304
Number of 6-input LUTs	92.152
Number of DSP slices (18 × 25 multipliers)	180
Available block RAM	4.824kbit
Number of DMA channels	3
Number of logical interrupts	32

Memory

Nonvolatile	32 GB minimum
DDR3 system memory	2 GB minimum

The cRIO-9082 provides the following ports and connectors:

- | | |
|---------------------------------|--------------------------|
| 1. Power Connector | 5. MXI Express Connector |
| 2. RJ-50 RS-485 Serial Port | 6. VGA Video Connector |
| 3. USB Ports 1-4 | 7. RS-232 Serial Port |
| 4. RJ-45 Ethernet Ports 1 and 2 | |

Figure 2.5: Connector Pane Compact Rio 9082

USB Ports

Number of ports	4
USB interface	USB 2.0, Hi-Speed
Maximum data rate	480 Mb/s per port
Maximum current	500 mA

Network/Ethernet Port

Number of ports	2
Network interface	10Base-T, 100Base-TX, and 1000Base-T Ethernet
Compatibility	IEEE 802.3
Communication rates	10 Mbit/s, 100 Mbit/s, 1000 Mbit/s auto-negotiated
Maximum cabling distance	100 m/segment

2.4 Compact Rio 9034

Figure 2.6: Compact Rio9034

Powered by the NI LabVIEW reconfigurable I/O (RIO) architecture, NI CompactRIO combines an open embedded architecture with small size, extreme ruggedness, and hot-swappable industrial I/O modules. Each system contains an FPGA for custom timing, triggering, and processing with a wide array of modular I/O to meet any embedded application requirement.

Compact Rio architecture is as follows:

Figure 2.7: Compact Rio9034 Architecture

The following specifications are typical for the -20 °C to 55 °C operating temperature range unless otherwise noted.

Processor

CPU	Intel Atom E3845
Number of cores	4
CPU frequency	1.91 GHz
On-die L2 cache	2MB (shared)

Software requirements

Application software	
LabVIEW	LabVIEW 2014 or later LabVIEW Real-Time Module 2014 or later LabVIEW FPGA Module 2014 or later
Driver software	NI-RIO Device Drivers August 2014 or later

Internal Real Time Clock

Accuracy	200 ppm; 40 ppm at 25 °C
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Reconfigurable FPGA

FPGA type	Xilinx Kintex-7 7K325T
Number of flip flops	407,600
Number of 6-input LUTs	203,800
Number of DSP slices (18 × 25 multipliers)	840
Available block RAM	16.020 kbit
Number of DMA channels	16
Number of logical interrupts	32

Memory

Nonvolatile	
SD removable (user supplied)	Up to 32GB
Solid-state drive	16GB

Volatile	
Processor memory	
Density	2GB
Type	DDR3L
Maximum theoretical data rate	10.67 GB/s
FPGA memory	
Density	128 MB
Type	DDR3
Maximum theoretical data rate	1.6 GB/s
Data throughput	
System memory to SD removable storage	10 MB/s
Module slots to system memory	20 MB/s, application- and system-dependent

The cRIO-9034 provides the following ports and connectors:

- | | |
|---------------------------------|---------------------------------|
| 1. RJ-45 Gigabit Ethernet Ports | 5. RS-485/422 (DTE) Serial Port |
| 2. Power Connector | 6. Mini DisplayPort |
| 3. SD Card Removable Storage | 7. USB Host Ports |
| 4. RS-232 Serial Port | 8. USB Device Port |

Figure 2.8: Connector Pane Compact Rio 9034

USB Ports

Number of ports	4
USB interface	USB 2.0, Hi-Speed
Maximum data rate	480 Mb/s per port
Maximum current	500 mA

Network/Ethernet Port

Number of ports	2
Network interface	10Base-T, 100Base-TX, and 1000Base-T Ethernet
Compatibility	IEEE 802.3
Communication rates	10 Mbit/s, 100 Mbit/s, 1000 Mbit/s auto-negotiated
Maximum cabling distance	100 m/segment

2.5 NI C Series Modules Overview

Figure 2.9: NI C Series Modules

NI C Series modules are designed to provide high-accuracy measurements to meet the demands of advanced DAQ and control applications. Each module contains measurement-specific signal conditioning to connect to an array of sensors and signals, bank and channel-to-channel isolation options, and support for wide temperature ranges to meet a variety of application and environmental needs all in a single rugged package. You can choose from more than 100 C Series modules for measurement, control, and communication to connect your applications to any sensor on any bus. Most C Series I/O modules work with both the NI CompactDAQ and NI CompactRIO

platforms. The modules are identical, and you can move them from one platform to the other with no modification.

2.5.1 NI 9467 GPS Timestamping and Synchronization Module

- Pulse per second (PPS) accuracy of ± 100 ns, >99 percent typical
- SMA female antenna connector type (antenna sold separately)
- +5 VDC (up to 30 mA) for active GPS antenna
- Returns stationary global position after self-survey NI CompactRIO support only

Figure 2.10: NI9467

2.5.2 NI 9225

3-Channel, 300 Vrms, 24-Bit Simultaneous, Channel-to-Channel Isolated Analog Input Module

Figure 2.11

The NI 9225 analog input channels are floating with respect to earth ground and each other. The incoming analog signal on each channel is conditioned, buffered, and then

sampled by a 24-bit Delta-Sigma ADC. Each channel provides an independent signal path and ADC, enabling you to sample all three channels simultaneously. Refer to Figure 2.8 for an illustration of the circuitry for one channel of the NI 9225.

Figure 2.12: Input Circuitry for One Channel of the NI 9225

The frequency of a master timebase (f_M) controls the data rate (f_s) of the NI 9225. The NI 9225 includes an internal master timebase with a frequency of 12.8 MHz, but the module also can accept an external master timebase or export its own master timebase. To synchronize the data rate of an NI 9225 with other modules that use master timebases to control sampling, all of the modules must share a single master timebase source. The following equation provides the available data rates of the NI 9225:

$$f_s = \frac{f_M}{256 * n}$$

where n is any integer from 1 to 31. However, the data rate must remain within the appropriate data rate range. When using the internal master timebase of 12.8 MHz, the result is data rates of 50 kSamples/s, 25 kSample/s, 16.667 kSample/s, and so on down to 1.613 kS/s, depending on the value of n. When using an external timebase with a frequency other than 12.8 MHz, the NI 9225 has a different set of data rates.

Specifications

The following specifications are typical for the range -40 to 70 °C unless otherwise noted. All voltages are relative to the AI- signal on each channel unless otherwise noted.

Number of channels	3 analog input channels
ADC resolution	24 bits
Type of ADC	Delta-Sigma (with analog prefiltering)

Sampling mode	Simultaneous Internal master timebase (f_M)
Frequency	12.8 MHz
Accuracy	± 100 ppm max
Data rate range (fs) using internal master timebase	
Minimum	1.613 kSamples/s
Maximum	50 kSamples/s
Operating voltage ranges	
Minimum	294 Vrms
Typical	300 Vrms
Overvoltage protection	± 450 VDC
Input coupling	DC
Input impedance (AI+ to AI-)	1M Ω
Accuracy	

Measurement Conditions	Percent of Reading (Gain Error)	Percent of Range* (Offset Error)
Calibrated max (-40 to 70 °C)	$\pm 0.23\%$	$\pm 0.05\%$
Calibrated typ (25 °C, ± 5 °C)	$\pm 0.05\%$	$\pm 0.008\%$
Calibrated max (25 °C, ± 15 °C)	$\pm 0.084\%$	$\pm 0.016\%$
Uncalibrated max (-40 to 70 °C)	$\pm 1.6\%$	$\pm 0.66\%$
Uncalibrated typ (25 °C, ± 5 °C)	$\pm 0.4\%$	$\pm 0.09\%$
* Range equals 425 V.		

Table 1: Accuracy of NI9225 in different Measurement Conditions

Input noise	2 mVrms
Stability	
Gain drift	± 10 ppm/°C
Offset drift	± 970 μ V/°C
Phase match	
Ch-to-ch, max	0.035°/kHz
Module-to-module, max	0.035°/kHz + 360° · fin/f _M
Phase linearity (fs = 50 kSamples/s)	0.22° max

2.5.3 NI 9227

4-Channel, 5 Arms, 24-Bit, Simultaneous, Channel-to-Channel Isolated Analog Input Module

Figure 2.13

The NI 9227 analog input channels are floating with respect to earth ground and each other. The incoming analog signal on each channel is conditioned, buffered, and then sampled by a 24-bit Delta-Sigma ADC. Each channel provides an independent signal path and ADC, enabling you to sample all four channels simultaneously. Refer to Figure 5 for an illustration of the circuitry for one channel of the NI 9227.

Figure 2.14: Input Circuitry for One Channel of the NI 9227

The frequency of a master timebase (f_M) controls the data rate (f_s) of the NI 9227. The NI 9227 includes an internal master timebase with a frequency of 12.8 MHz, but the module also can accept an external master timebase or export its own master timebase. To synchronize the data rate of an NI 9227 with other modules that use master timebases to control sampling, all of the modules must share a single master timebase source.

The following equation provides the available data rates of the NI 9227:

$$f_s = \frac{f_M}{256 * n}$$

where n is any integer from 1 to 31. However, the data rate must remain within the appropriate data rate range. When using the internal master timebase of 12.8 MHz, the result is data rates of 50 kSamples/s, 25 kSample/s, 16.667 kSample/s, and so on down to 1.613 kS/s, depending on the value of n. When using an external timebase with a frequency other than 12.8 MHz, the NI 9225 has a different set of data rates.

Specifications

The following specifications are typical for the range -40 to 70 °C unless otherwise noted. All currents are relative to the AI- signal on each channel unless otherwise noted.

Number of channels	4 analog input channels
ADC resolution	24 bits
Type of ADC	Delta-Sigma (with analog prefiltering)
Sampling mode	Simultaneous Internal master timebase (f _M)
Frequency	12.8 MHz
Accuracy	±100 ppm max
Data rate range (f _s) using internal master timebase	
Minimum	1.613 kSamples/s
Maximum	50 kSamples/s
Overcurrent handling	10 Arms for 1 s max with 19 s minimum cool down time at 5 Arms
Instantaneous measuring range	
Minimum	14.051 A peak
Typical	14.977 A peak, at 23 ±5 °C
Input coupling	DC

Input impedance (AI+ to AI-) 12mΩ
 Input noise (fs = 50 kSamples/s) 400 μArms

Accuracy at safe operating range of 5 Arms

Measurement Conditions	Percent of Reading (Gain Error)	Percent of Range* (Offset Error)
Calibrated max (-40 to 70 °C)	±0.37%	±0.18%
Calibrated typ (23 °C, ±5 °C)	±0.1%	±0.05%
Uncalibrated max (-40 to 70 °C)	±5.0%	±2.4%
Uncalibrated typ (23 °C, ±5 °C)	±2.5%	±1.0%
* Range equals 7.07 A peak (5 A _{rms}).		

Table 2: Accuracy of NI9227 in different Measurement Conditions

Stability

Gain drift ±21 ppm/°C

Offset drift ±51 μA/°C

Phase match

Ch-to-ch, max 0.1°/kHz

Module-to-module, max 0.1°/kHz + 360° · fin/fM

Phase linearity (fs = 50 kSamples/s) 0.1 max

2.5.4 NI 9239

4 AI, ± 10 V, 24 Bit, 50 kS/s/ch Simultaneous

Figure 2.15

The NI 9239 is an analog input module for use in NI CompactDAQ or CompactRIO systems. Each channel provides a ± 10 V measurement range at a 24-bit resolution. The NI 9239 outputs 50 kSamples/s of data at the maximum sampling rate. Designed for both speed and accuracy, the NI 9239 is an effective general-purpose analog module because of its resolution, sample rate, and input range.

Figure 2.16: NI 9239 Input Circuitry

Input signals on each channel are conditioned, buffered, and then sampled by an ADC. Each AI channel provides an independent signal path and ADC, enabling you to sample all channels simultaneously.

The frequency of a master timebase (f_M) controls the data rate (f_s) of the NI 9239. The NI 9239 includes an internal master timebase with a frequency of 12.8 MHz, but the module also can accept an external master timebase or export its own master timebase.

To synchronize the data rate of an NI 9239 with other modules that use master timebases to control sampling, all of the modules must share a single master timebase source. The following equation provides the available data rates of the NI 9239:

$$f_s = \frac{f_M}{256 * n}$$

where n is any integer from 1 to 31. However, the data rate must remain within the appropriate data rate range. When using the internal master timebase of 12.8 MHz, the result is data rates of 50 kSamples/s, 25 kSample/s, 16.667 kSample/s, and so on down to 1.613 kS/s, depending on the value of n. When using an external timebase with a frequency other than 12.8 MHz, the NI 9239 has a different set of data rates.

Specifications

The following specifications are typical for the range -40 to 70 °C unless otherwise noted. All voltages are relative to the AI- signal on each channel unless otherwise noted.

Number of channels	4 analog input channels
ADC resolution	24 bits
Type of ADC	Delta-Sigma (with analog prefiltering)
Sampling mode	Simultaneous Internal master timebase (f_M)
Frequency	12.8 MHz
Accuracy	±100 ppm max
Data rate range (fs) using internal master timebase	
Minimum	1.613 kSamples/s
Maximum	50 kSamples/s
Input voltage ranges (AI+ to AI-)	
Nominal	±10 V
Typical	±10.52 V
Minimum	±10.3 V
Overvoltage protection	±100 V

Input coupling DC
 Input impedance (AI+ to AI-) 1MΩ

Accuracy at safe operating range of 10 Vrms

Measurement Conditions		Percent of Reading (Gain Error)	Percent of Range ² (Offset Error)
Calibrated	Typical (25 °C, ±5 °C)	±0.03%	±0.008%
	Maximum (-40 °C to 70 °C)	±0.13%	±0.06%
Uncalibrated ³	Typical (25 °C, ±5 °C)	±0.3%	±0.11%
	Maximum (-40 °C to 70 °C)	±1.4%	±0.70%

Table 3: Accuracy of NI9239 in different Measurement Conditions

Input noise 70 μVrms
 Stability
 Gain drift ±5 ppm/°C
 Offset drift ±26 μV/°C
 Phase mismatch
 Ch-to-ch, max 0.075°/kHz maximum
 Module-to-module, max $(0.075^\circ/\text{kHz} \cdot f_{in}) + (360^\circ \cdot f_{in}/f_M)$
 Phase nonlinearity (fs = 50 kSamples/s) 0.11° maximum

2.6 FLUKE 6135A / PMU CAL

The Fluke Calibration 6135A/PMUCAL Phasor Measurement Unit Calibration System (the Product or Calibration System) is a measurement and calibration device used to calibrate and test a PMU (Phasor Measurement Unit).

Figure 2.17: Fluke 6135A / PMU CAL

Features of the Calibration System:

- Simulate static and dynamic conditions that a UUT can experience in a power grid.
- Test a UUT against the performance standards written in IEEE C37.118.1-2011 (Synchrophasor Measurements for Power Systems) and IEEE C37.118.2 (Synchrophasor Data Transfer for Power Systems).
- Quickly set up and configure a UUT for calibration with a single, side mounted input panel.
- Remotely calibrate and test a UUT from a desktop PC using the PMU Calibration Software.
- Manually run single tests or use the factory built-in automated test procedures.
- Produce formal calibration reports in a format that can be easily printed or shared electronically.

The Calibration System is made up of six individual devices that are interconnected inside a server rack (see Figure 2.17). See the “Components of the Calibration System” for more information about each individual device. The Fluke 6105A and two 6106A together comprise a 6135A. The Fluke 6135A is a source of precision three phase voltage and current signals. These precise signals must be related to Universal Coordinated Time (UTC) to be useful for calibration of PMU UUTs. The 6135A/PMU System Timing Unit uses accurate time from the GPS receiver to align the 6135A output frequency and phase angles to meet the requirements of the PMU calibration standard: IEEE C37.118.1 - 2011. A Client software application package on a laptop or desktop computer (not shown) lets the operator communicate with the Server PC via a WAN (wide area network) connection. The Server PC controls the equipment as required by calibration procedures located on the Client computer.

2.7 Fluke 6105A

The Fluke Electrical Power Standards, “the Instruments” or “The Instrument”, are precise instruments for the calibration of Watthour meters and energy reference standards and measuring devices used to determine the magnitude and quality of power supplied to consumers. The range of power standards includes the 6100B, 6105A Master Instruments and 6101B and 6106A Auxiliary Instruments.

Figure 2.18: Fluke 6105A

The Instruments can each be used to provide a single phase of electrical power quality and energy. Adding one to three 6101B or 6106A Auxiliary Instruments extends a

system to up to four phases. For greater flexibility, the 6100B and 6105A Master units can also be configured as Auxiliaries by connecting one cable externally.

The following sections give the Instrument's general and detailed specifications.

Operating temperature	5 °C - 35 °C
Calibration temperature (tcal) range	16 °C - 30 °C
Storage temperature	0 °C - 50 °C
Transit temperature	-20 °C - 60 °C
Warm up time	1 hour
Voltage/Current amplitude setting resolution	6 digits
Range of fundamental frequencies	16 Hz - 850 Hz
Line frequency locking	45 Hz - 65.9 Hz at user's discretion
Frequency accuracy	±10 ppm
Frequency setting resolution	0.1 Hz
Warm up time to full accuracy	1 hour or twice the time since last warmed up
Settling time following change to the output	0 to 10 seconds
Nominal angle between voltage phases	120 °
Nominal angle between voltage and current of a phase	0 °
Phase angle setting	±180 °, ± π radians [1]
Phase angle setting resolution	0.001 °, 0.00001 radians [1]
Maximum number of voltage harmonics	100 including the 1st (fundamental frequency)
Maximum number of current harmonics	100 including the 1st (fundamental frequency)

[1] Switching between phase set in degrees, phase set in radians and back may not be consistent because of calculation rounding errors.

Amplitude / Frequency Limits

Figure 2.19

- If the 50 A or 80 A option is fitted, the range minimum settable fundamental frequency is 40 Hz and the maximum harmonic frequency is 3 kHz.
- Although the minimum settable fundamental frequency is 16 Hz, modulated waveforms may generate frequency components below that, including DC.
- A DC component of up to 50 % of range may be added to all voltage and current ranges except 50 A and 80 A.
- If the bandwidth limit is enabled, maximum frequency is 1.5 kHz.

- Voltage Range Limits and Burden

Full Range (FR)	23 V	45 V	90 V	180 V	360 V	650 V ^[4]	1008 V
Max peak ^{[1][2]}	32.5 V	63.6 V	127.2 V	254.5 V	509 V	919 V	1425 V
Maximum Burden (peak current) ^[3]	1 A	1 A	1 A	1 A	1 A	1 A	71 mA
Maximum Burden (RMS current) ^[3]	500 mA	500 mA	500 mA	250 mA	150 mA	110 mA	60 mA

[1] These values apply to sinusoidal, distorted and modulated wave-shapes.
 [2] Voltage harmonic phase angle significantly affects the peak value of a non-sinusoidal waveform.
 [3] To achieve specifications in 4-wire sense, resistance in the sense lead must be less than 1 Ω and resistance in the power leads less than 1.5 Ω.
 [4] 6105A and 6101B only.
 [5] The peak current cannot be sustained and is dependent on the voltage level at which it is requested. It will not be possible to achieve this current when the output is at 0 V but it will be achievable as the voltage approaches the peak level of the waveform. High peak current capability is provided to drive meters that take pulses of current from the signal.

- Voltage Sine Amplitude Specifications

Ranges	Frequency	Voltage ^[5]	6105A & 6106A 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[4] ±5 °C ± (ppm of output + mV) ^{[1][6]}		6100B & 6101B 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[4] ±5 °C ± (ppm of output + mV) ^{[1][6]}		6100B, 6101B, 6105A & 6106A Open Loop 24-Hour Stability ± (ppm of output + mV) ^{[2][3]}	
1.0 V - 23 V	45 Hz - 65 Hz	15 V - 17 V	42	0	112	1	75	0.8
		1.0 V - 23 V	42	0.2				
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	60	0.2					
3 V - 45 V	45 Hz - 65 Hz	28 V - 32 V	42	0	112	2	75	0.8
		3 V - 45 V	42	0.4				
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	60	0.4					
6.3 V - 90 V	45 Hz - 65 Hz	56 V - 64 V	42	0	112	2.2	75	0.8
		6.3 V - 90 V	42	0.8				
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	60	0.8					
13 V - 180 V	45 Hz - 65 Hz	110 V - 128 V	44	0	112	4.4	75	1.5
		13 V - 180 V	44	1.6				
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	60	1.6					
25 V - 360 V	45 Hz - 65 Hz	215 V - 246 V	44	0	112	8.8	75	3
		25 V - 360 V	60	3.2				
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	3.2					
46 V - 650 V	45 Hz - 65 Hz	425 V - 490 V	44	0	-	-	75	6
		46 V - 650 V	60	5.8				
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	5.8					
70 V - 1008 V	45 Hz - 65 Hz	740 V - 850 V	44	0	150	26	75	10
		70 V - 1008 V	60	10				
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	10					

[1] Four-wire sense only, for two-wire operation, add an additional voltage = 0.3 Ω x maximum burden current to the accuracy specification.
 [2] For ±1 °C and constant load and connection conditions.
 [3] When Flicker, Fluctuating harmonics, Dip/Swell or Interharmonics are applied, Open Loop Stability specification must be added to the 1-year accuracy specification as described in "Open and Closed Loop Operation".
 [4] tcal = temperature of last calibration.
 [5] Output levels less than the range minimum can be set but are not specified.
 [6] These specifications assume a "sampling" measuring instrument. Some rms sensing instruments have voltage input bandwidths of several MHz. The 6100B specification should be expanded by the non-harmonic noise floor in the "Voltage Distortion and Noise" table for rms sensing devices.

- Voltage DC and Harmonic Amplitude Specifications

Range	Output ^{[4][5]}	Frequency	6105A & 6106A 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[4] ±5 °C ±(ppm of output + mV) _{[1][6]}		6100B & 6101B 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[4] ±5 °C ±(ppm of output + mV) _{[1][6]}		Open Loop 24-Hour Stability ± (ppm of output + mV) ^{[2][3]}	
1.0 V - 23 V	0 V - 11.5 V	DC	91	2	122	5	75	1.8
	0 V - 6.9 V	16 Hz - 850 Hz	58	1	122	1	75	0.8
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	451	1	512	1	150	0.8
3 V - 45 V	0 V - 22.5 V	DC	91	4	122	10	75	3.3
	0 V - 13.5 V	16 Hz - 850 Hz	58	2	122	2	75	0.8
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	451	2	512	2	150	0.8
6.3 V - 90 V	0 V - 45 V	DC	91	8	122	24	75	8
	0 V - 27 V	16 Hz - 850 Hz	60	2.2	122	2.2	75	0.8
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	451	2.2	512	2.2	150	0.8
13 V - 180 V	0 V - 90 V	DC	91	16	122	50	75	15
	0 V - 54 V	16 Hz - 850 Hz	60	4.4	122	4.4	75	1.5
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	451	4.4	512	4.4	150	1.5
25 V - 360 V	0 V - 180 V	DC	91	32	122	100	75	30
	0 V - 108 V	16 Hz - 850 Hz	60	12	122	12	75	3
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	451	12	512	12	150	3
46 V - 650 V	0 V - 325 V	DC	92	60	-	-	75	65
	0 V - 195 V	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	22	-	-	75	6
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	451	22	-	-	150	6
70 V - 1008 V	0 V - 504 V	DC	92	100	166	300	75	100
	0 V - 302 V	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	33	166	33	75	10
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	451	33	524	33	150	10
<p>[1] Four-wire sense only, for two-wire operation, add an additional voltage = 0.3 Ω x maximum burden current to the accuracy specification.</p> <p>[2] For ±1 °C and constant load and connection conditions.</p> <p>[3] When Flicker, Fluctuating harmonics, Dip/Swell or Interharmonics are applied, "Open loop" stability specification must be added to the 1-year accuracy specification as described in "Open and Closed Loop Operation".</p> <p>[4] These specifications are only applicable if the combined voltage rms output is greater than the range minimum. If the combined output is below the range minimum the output is not specified.</p> <p>[5] The maximum value for a single harmonic (2nd to 100th) below 2850 Hz is 30 % of range. See "Amplitude/Frequency Limits" for profile above 2850 Hz.</p> <p>[6] tcal = temperature of last calibration.</p>								

- Current Range Limits

Full Range (FR)	0.25 A	0.5 A	1 A	2 A	5 A	10 A	21 A	50 A	80 A
Max Peak ^{[1][2]}	0.353 A	0.707 A	1.414 A	2.828 A	7.07 A	14.14 A	29.7 A	70.7	113 A
Maximum Compliance Voltage at FR (Vpk) ^{[3][4]}	14 V	14 V	14 V	14 V	14 V	14 V	12.5 V	3 V	2 V
Maximum Inductive Load, Hi Bandwidth ^[5]	300 μH	300 μH	300 μH	300 μH	300 μH	30 μH	30 μH	30 μH	30 μH
Maximum Inductive Load, Lo Bandwidth ^{[5][6]}	2 mH	2 mH	1 mH	1 mH	500 μH	360 μH	500 μH	250 μH	250 μH

[1] These values apply to sinusoidal, distorted and modulated wave-shapes.
 [2] Current harmonic phase angle significantly affects the peak value of a non-sinusoidal waveform.
 [3] Above 450 Hz, the instrument will drive current outputs that develop maximum compliance voltage across the load, but an "adder" to the accuracy specification in "Current DC and Harmonic Amplitude Specifications" and "Current Distortion and Noise" may be required. Calculation of the "adders" is described below.
 [4] Compliance voltage at the end of connecting leads will be reduced by the IR drop in the cables.
 [5] The current output will remain stable with the inductive loads shown but may not be able to drive that inductance at all current/frequency/harmonic combinations due to voltage burden limitations. The inductive load due to connecting cables may be decreased by reducing their loop area, for example, by tying the cables together or shortening the cables.
 [6] In low bandwidth mode maximum frequency is 1.5 kHz.

- Current Sine Amplitude Specifications

Range (Amps)	Frequency	Current (Amps) ^[4]	6105A & 6106A 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[3] ±5 °C ±(ppm of output + μA)		6100B & 6101B 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[3] ±5 °C ±(ppm of output + μA)		Open Loop 24-Hour Stability ±(ppm of output + μA) ^{[1][2]}	
0.25 A	45 Hz to 65 Hz	0.1 A - 0.25 A	46	2.5	139	6	75	3
		0.25 A	46	1.5	130	6	75	3
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	0.01 A - 0.1 A	60	5	139	6	75	3
		0.1 A - 0.25 A	60	5	130	6	75	3
0.5 A	45 Hz to 65 Hz	0.2 A - 0.5 A	46	5	139	12	75	5
		0.5 A	46	3	130	12	75	5
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	0.05 A - 0.2 A	61	10	139	12	75	5
		0.2 A - 0.5 A	61	10	130	12	75	5
1 A	45 Hz to 65 Hz	0.4 A - 1.0 A	47	10	139	24	75	10
		1 A	47	6	130	24	75	10
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	0.1 A - 0.4 A	61	20	139	24	75	10
		0.4 A - 1 A	61	20	130	24	75	10
2 A	45 Hz to 65 Hz	0.8 - 2 A	46	20	139	48	75	20
		2 A	46	12	130	48	75	20
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	0.2 A - 0.8 A	61	40	139	48	75	20
		0.8 A - 2 A	61	40	130	48	75	20

[1] For ±1 °C and constant load and connection conditions.
 [2] When Flicker, Fluctuating harmonics, Dip/Swell or Interharmonics are applied, "Open loop" stability specification must be added to the 1-year accuracy specification as described in "Open and Closed Loop Operation".
 [3] tcal = temperature of last calibration.
 [4] Output levels less than the range minimum can be set but are not specified.
 [5] These specifications assume a "sampling" measuring instrument. Some rms sensing instruments have voltage input bandwidths of several MHz. The 6100B specification should be expanded by the non-harmonic noise floor in "Current Distortion and Noise" for rms sensing devices.
 [6] Settling time (TS) of 21 A, 50 A, and 80 A ranges depends on rms output as a proportion of full range and can be calculated from: TS = %FR2 x 180 seconds. Settling magnitude will not exceed 50 ppm at FR.

Range (Amps)	Frequency	Current (Amps) ^[4]	6105A & 6106A 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[3] ±5 °C ±(ppm of output + μA)		6100B & 6101B 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[2] ±5 °C ±(ppm of output + μA)		Open Loop 24-Hour Stability ±(ppm of output + μA) ^{[1][2]}	
5 A	45 Hz to 65 Hz	2 - 5 A	49	50	139	120	75	50
		5 A	49	30	130	120	75	50
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	0.5 A - 2 A	64	100	139	120	75	50
		2 A - 5 A	64	100	130	120	75	50
10 A	45 Hz to 65 Hz	4 - 10 A	49	100	191	240	75	50
		10 A	49	60	164	240	75	50
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	1 A - 4 A	65	200	191	240	75	100
		4 A - 10 A	65	200	164	240	75	100
21 A	45 Hz to 65 Hz	8 A - 21 A	49	200	213	720	75	300
		21 A	49	120	189	720	75	300
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	2 A - 8 A	69	400	213	720	75	300
		8 A - 21 A	69	400	189	720	75	300
50 A	45 Hz to 65 Hz	20 A - 50 A	49	500	213	1800	500	750
		50 A	49	300	189	1800	500	750
	16 Hz - 850 Hz	3.2 A - 20 A	74	1000	213	1800	500	750
		20 A - 50 A	74	1000	189	1800	500	750
80 A	40 Hz - 450 Hz	8 A - 32 A	106	2800	265	2800	1000	1200
		32 A - 80 A	106	2800	250	2800	1000	1200
	450 Hz - 850 Hz	8 A - 32 A	112	2800	300	2800	1000	1200
		32 A - 80 A	118	2800	280	2800	1000	1200
<p>[1] For ±1 °C and constant load and connection conditions.</p> <p>[2] When Flicker, Fluctuating harmonics, Dip/Swell or Interharmonics are applied, "Open loop" stability specification must be added to the 1-year accuracy specification as described in "Open and Closed Loop Operation".</p> <p>[3] tcal = temperature of last calibration.</p> <p>[4] Output levels less than the range minimum can be set but are not specified.</p> <p>[5] These specifications assume a "sampling" measuring instrument. Some rms sensing instruments have voltage input bandwidths of several MHz. The 6100B specification should be expanded by the non-harmonic noise floor in "Current Distortion and Noise" for rms sensing devices.</p> <p>[6] Settling time (TS) of 21 A, 50 A, and 80 A ranges depends on rms output as a proportion of full range and can be calculated from: TS = %FR2 x 180 seconds. Settling magnitude will not exceed 50 ppm at FR.</p>								

- Current DC and Harmonic Amplitude Specifications

Range	Current ^[4]	Frequency	6105A & 6106A 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[3] ±5 °C ± (ppm of output + μA)		6100B & 6101B 1-Year Accuracy, tcal ^[3] ±5 °C ± (ppm of output + μA)		Open Loop 24- Hour Stability ± (ppm of output + μA) ^{[1][2]}	
0.01 A - 0.25 A	0 A - 0.125 A	DC	89	25	139	75	100	11
	0 A - 0.075 A	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	5	139	6	75	3
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	401	5	400	6	150	3
0.05 A - 0.5 A	0 A - 0.25 A	DC	89	50	139	150	100	22
	0 A - 0.15 A	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	10	139	12	75	5
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	401	10	400	12	150	5
0.1 A - 1 A	0 A - 0.5 A	DC	89	100	139	300	100	45
	0 A - 0.3 A	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	20	139	24	75	10
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	401	20	400	24	150	10
0.2 A - 2 A	0 A - 1 A	DC	89	200	139	600	100	90
	0 A - 0.6 A	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	40	182	48	75	20
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	401	40	400	48	150	20
0.5 A - 5 A	0 A - 2.5 A	DC	89	500	139	1500	100	225
	0 A - 1.5 A	16 Hz - 850 Hz	61	100	139	120	75	50
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	401	100	400	120	150	50
1 A - 10 A	0 A - 5 A	DC	89	1000	191	3000	100	450
	0 A - 3 A	16 Hz - 850 Hz	64	200	191	240	75	100
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	402	200	400	240	150	100
2 A - 21 A	0 A - 10 A	DC	90	2000	191	6000	100	900
	0 A - 6 A	16 Hz - 850 Hz	65	400	191	720	75	300
		850 Hz - 6 kHz	402	400	400	720	150	300
5 A - 50 A	0 A - 15 A	16 Hz - 850 Hz	69	1000	250	2800	500	750
		850 Hz - 3 kHz	403	1000	400	2800	750	1200
8 A - 80 A	0 A - 24 A	16 Hz - 850 Hz	112	2000	265	2800	500	1200
		850 Hz - 3 kHz	405	2000	400	2800	750	1200

[1] For ±1 °C and constant load and connection conditions.
[2] When Flicker, Fluctuating harmonics, Dip/Swell or Interharmonics are applied, "Open loop" stability specification must be added to the 1-year accuracy specification as described in "Open and Closed Loop Operation".
[3] tcal = temperature of last calibration.
[4] These specifications are only applicable if the combined voltage rms output is greater than the range minimum. If the combined output is below the range minimum the output is not specified.
[5] The maximum value for a single harmonic (2nd to 100th) below 2850 Hz is 30 % of range. See "Amplitude/Frequency Limits" for profile above 2850 Hz.

2.8 PXI Chassis with NI 5422 and NI 6683H modules

PXI is a rugged PC-based platform for measurement and automation systems. PXI combines PCI electrical-bus features with the modular, Eurocard packaging of Compact-PCI and then adds specialized synchronization buses and key software features. PXI is both a high-performance and low-cost deployment platform for applications such as manufacturing test, military and aerospace, machine monitoring, automotive, and industrial test.

As the backbone of your PXI system, the chassis provides the power, cooling, and communication buses of PCI and PCI Express for your controller and modules. PXI chassis are available in a variety of configurations such as low noise, high temperature, and low- to high-slot count. They also offer a range of I/O module slot types, integrated peripherals such as LCD displays, and more.

PXI Chassis are compatible with PXI, PXI Express, and PXI hybrid modules and meet the cooling requirements of the most power-demanding PXI modules.

Figure 2.20 PXI chassis, with two modules NI 5422

The module that we have chosen for generation is NI PXI 5422.

The PXI 5422 is an 80 MHz arbitrary waveform generator capable of generating user-defined, arbitrary waveforms and standard functions including sine, square, triangle, and ramp.

This arbitrary waveform generator can generate signals from -6 V to +6 V and uses direct digital synthesis (DDS) to precisely generate waveforms. The PXI 5422 also features advanced synchronization and data streaming capabilities.

Figure 2.21: NI 5422 module

The PXI-6683 timing and synchronization modules synchronize PXI and PXI Express systems using GPS, IEEE 1588, and IRIG-B to perform synchronous events. The PXI-6683 can generate events and clock signals at specified synchronized future times and timestamp input events with the synchronized system time. The PXI-6683 features an onboard temperature-compensated crystal oscillator (TCXO) that can be disciplined to GPS, IEEE 1588, and IRIG-B for long-term stability. You also can use the PXI-6683 to route clock signals and triggers with low skew within a PXI chassis or between multiple chassis, providing you a method for synchronizing multiple devices in a PXI system.

Figure 2.22: NI 6683 module

**CHAPTER 3: DEVELOPED
ALGORITHMS AND SOFTWARE
IMPLEMENTATION**

3.1 General overview on the implemented algorithms

As mentioned in the previous chapters, the main feature of this work of thesis is to realize a high accuracy measurement system for current and voltage signals sampled in defined instants of time. For applications that require this accuracy, is impossible to use the internal clock of the acquisition modules or, in specific case, of an FPGA as reference because the value of the clock frequency deviates (for drifts and offset) from the nominal value of a non-negligible quantity.

For this work of thesis, we use Pulse Per Second (PPS) Signal as time reference, that is a digital signal generated by a GPS receiver that very precisely indicates the beginning of a second with an uncertainty, in our case, of 100 ns. Unfortunately, the NI9467 GPS receiver module is not a disciplined oscillator, therefore it is not possible to use its time base as clock for the acquisition modules that would allow to know all the real sampling time instants. Therefore, it is necessary to develop an estimate of the real time instants in which the input signals are sampled and, by means of an interpolation, to perform a resampling at the desired time instants. On these processed data, it is now possible to perform amplitude, phase and frequency measurements of the synchophasor through a Discrete Fourier Transform interpolated in frequency domain (IPDFT).

Figure 3.1: Flow Chart of implemented algorithm

As told in chapter 2, this measurement device is composed by two processing units, FPGA and CPU, that communicate each other via two hardware First In First Out (FIFO) memory structures. In next paragraphs algorithms and their software implementations both for FPGA and Controller module will be explained.

3.2 Synchronization technique

One of the most interesting aspects among those dealt with in this thesis work is certainly the one related to synchronization. In order to be able to instantly analyze the voltage and current behavior over a wide area of railway network, it is necessary for each measurement device to refer to a universal time. Therefore the challenge is to get information about the signals at the same time instants for all the devices distributed in the substations and on trains. The time reference is provided by a GPS receiver which is able to generate a Pulse Per Second (PPS) signal with high accuracy and, with a systematic delay, to provide in International Atomic Time format (TAI, from the French name temps atomique international) the number of nanoseconds since 1 January 1970 at 12.00 to that PPS. Unfortunately this device is not able to generate a clock signal for the acquisition system, so the acquisition modulus's clocks (single for all), the FPGA clock and the external time reference are totally unrelated to each other. At this end it's necessary to develop a technique that allows to evaluate measurands in desired instant, or rather in instants equidistant of the nominal sampling time starting from the instant in which the PPS event occurs. In synchronized conditions, what are the behaviors of two acquisition systems in a defined interval between two events of 1-PPS are shown in Figure 3.2:

Figure 3.2: Ideal behaviour in synchronized conditions

In this case, considering a sample acquired for each arrow, the sampling time τ_s on both system is the nominal one and the first sample is taken in same instant of PPS event.

In these conditions, the sampling frequency could be calculated as:

$$f_{s1} = f_{s2} = N_s * 1Hz \text{ and } N_s * \tau_s = 1s$$

For applications like this that requires a high accuracy level, the difference between the nominal values of sampling frequency or system clock frequency with the real ones are not negligible, so these quantities must be measured. The Figure 3.3 shows the real behaviour of the acquisition systems and of the FPGA clock using as reference the time defined between two (1-PPS) event.

Figure 3.3: Real behaviour of system in not synchronized conditions

The difference between the ideal case and the real one, shown in Figure 3.3, can be seen in sampling time, different from nominal value, so in number of points between two 1-PPS event. Furthermore a non-null time interval is present between the moment in which the PPS event occurs and the first acquired sample of the window. In this case:

$$f_{s1} \neq f_{s2} \neq N_s * 1Hz \text{ and } N_s * \tau_s \neq 1s$$

Figure 3.4: Control information for synchronization technique

In figure 3.3 several information for the implementation of synchronization technique are shown:

- The number of system ticks between two PPS events. This number represents the real value of FPGA clock frequency (f_{clock})
- The number of samples acquired between two PPS events (N_s).
- Desynchronization time value (ds). This value represents the system clock ticks between last sample acquired and PPS event.
- Tick PPS[$i-1$], Tick PPS[i], Tick last sample[i] are the system tick value in PPS events and in last sample acquired event. [i] is the index of the seconds.

This information allows to estimate the real time instants in which each point of the interval is sampled. Considering that:

$$tick\ PPS[i] - tick\ PPS[i - 1] = N_s \tau_s + ds[i] - ds[i - 1] \quad (3.1)$$

$$\tau_s = \frac{1}{f_s} = \frac{\Delta tick\ last\ sample}{N_s} \quad (3.2)$$

where $ds[i] = tick\ PPS[i] - tick\ last\ sample[i]$ and f_s is the real sampling frequency.

3.3 Labview implementation on FPGA

In this paragraph the Labview implementation of the acquisition and synchronization algorithm is shown. This part of the software has been developed on FPGA for high performances level in parallel operations.

Figure 3.5: Flow chart of FPGA software

First the peripheral initialization is performed. The sampling frequencies for the acquisition modules are set and the first valid PPS is expected. The validity of a PPS is guaranteed by the presence of the GPS signal. The receiver module is certainly able to generate a PPS with a high accuracy even in the absence of GPS signal, but the prolonged absence of the latter could lead to drifts of the Real Time internal clock of the receiver module with consequent synchronization errors. For this reason, upon power-up, a synchronization with the external universal reference is required regardless of the previous state of the receiver module's clock. After this, the acquisition starts.

Figure 3.6: Labview implementation of Initialization and start acquisition

The Sample Loop has the task, for each iteration, to acquire one sample by every channel. Within this loop, a sample counter is updated to be read once per second, every time a PPS event occurs. Therefore this loop will have a rate corresponding to the sampling frequency, in this case, of 50 kHz. Another information that is memorized

by this loop is the tick value of the FPGA clock for each sample, but only the last sample is read before the new PPS event. Opportune barriers are introduced to avoid race condition on data storing at asynchronous PPS event.

Figure 3.7: Labview implementation of Samples Loop – Case False

Figure 3.8: Labview implementation of Samples Loop – Case True

There is a case structure because if the controller is not in execution, the hardware fifo on which the samples are stored are not downloaded and therefore is brought into a TIMEOUT state. At this point, the boolean variable "Flush indicator" becomes true and the system stops the acquisition remaining locked in the false case. When the controller starts, another boolean variable called "Restart", driven by the controller, becomes true and the system returns to the acquisition state. Obviously, before Restart becomes true, all the samples contained in the hardware queue are discarded. This

method has been chosen to avoid that the initialization phase is repeated every time the controller is restarted, as this phase can have execution times of even hours.

The synchronization loop has the task of waiting the PPS to arrive, read the samples counter, read the value of system tick of the last sample acquired and the value of system tick approximately in the same instant of PPS generation. After that, this loop waits the updating the data from GPS signal and send these information to another queue, known as “Control Queue”.

Figure 3.9: Labview implementation of synchronization loop

As we can see in Figure 3.7, a Boolean value reported as “Ok Status” is upload on the hardware FIFO.

As mentioned previously, the PPS signal is generated internally by the GPS receiver module but the generation accuracy depends on the presence of the GPS signal. By deepening, the generation of the PPS signal can occur in three different conditions:

- PPS generation in the presence of the GPS signal.

In this condition, the generation is controlled by the presence of the GPS signal because if the real time clock drift, on which the generation is based, presents a time error greater than a threshold imposed by the GPS, the module corrects the real time clock, confining the error maximum in a very narrow time frame.

- PPS generation without GPS signal.

The internal real time clock of the module generates the PPS in the same way seen before, but the error check and any correction presented in the previous case is not applicable. In this case, the generation is still considered valid, but the user is notified that the external reference has not been received.

- PPS generation in case of Timeout.

Generation occurs due to the interrupt absence from the synchronization module after 41 million FPGA clock hits. It is obvious that this entails a temporal distance between two successive PPSs greater than one second, therefore the processing must be managed differently from the two previous cases. In this case, the measurement is in any case reported to the user but is considered invalid

3.4 Labview implementation on Controller module

In this paragraph the Labview implementation of the interpolation method for resampling and the measurement algorithm is shown. This part of the software has been developed on Controller module because there is a high degree of flexibility in choosing how many and which channels to use.

Figure 3.10: Flow chart of Controller software

In initialization phase, both the hardware FIFOs contents are discarded.

Figure 3.11: Flushing hardware FIFOs

The Boolean variable “Flush indicator” indicates that hardware FIFOs are full and, in the subsequent loop every element are discarded. After that, with empty FIFOs, through the “Restart” command, the acquisition start but, in order to guarantee the

synchronization between the hardware FIFOs, the system waits until “Restart” variable becomes false.

The flow chart in Figure 3.8 shows how three main cyclic operations were performed in parallel after the initialization phase. In the first two loops, which start immediately after initialization, elements are taken from the hardware Fifo, specifically from the “Samples FIFO” and from the “Control FIFO”, and are downloaded in another two queues that are stored on the RAM memory. This type of operation is necessary because the size of the FIFOs used by the DMA is very limited. Furthermore, regardless of the number of channels selected for measurement, they are all brought to the controller module and are then discriminated. Therefore a high priority is implicit for this operation and higher the sampling frequency for each channel, the greater must be the speed with which the acquired samples must be brought to the queue in RAM. In the case treated, the loop is executed in 20 ms.

The implementation of the first main loop is the following:

- In section 1 (in red rectangle) number of elements in Samples FIFO are read. in order to avoid taking fewer points than the minimum number a case structure has been inserted.
- The points are inserted into a one-dimensional array, so taking eleven points means taking one point per channel. For this reason it is necessary to pick up a number of points that is an integer multiple of the number of channels installed on the Compact Rio. This is what has been implemented in Section 2.
- In section 3 the discrimination of the channels is implemented according to those activated by the user. In the first for loop the index of each active channel is collected in an array and the output is used to realize the two-dimensional array that has N_r rows with N_r is the number of elements for each channel and N_c columns with N_c number of channels active

Figure 3.12: First Main Loop

An example is given to better understand the operation of the for loop that allows the realization of the two-dimensional array.

Figure 3.13: discrimination loop

Suppose that 33 samples are extracted from the FIFO and that the active channels are channels 3 and 5. We distinguish the index of the external loop from the internal one using the letters X and Y respectively. The behavior shown for each iteration is as follows:

X	Y	ARRAY IN EXTERNAL FOR																			CHANNELS				
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	3	5
0	0	ARRAY IN INTERNAL FOR											CHANNEL	OUT INT FOR											
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	3	D											
0	1	ARRAY IN INTERNAL FOR											CHANNEL	OUT INT FOR											
		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	5	DF											
1	0	ARRAY IN INTERNAL FOR											CHANNEL	OUT INT FOR											
		L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	3	O											
1	1	ARRAY IN INTERNAL FOR											CHANNEL	OUT INT FOR											
		L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S	T	U	V	5	OP											
		OUT EXT FOR																							
		DF																							
		OP																							

In case of error, in case of Timeout of hardware FIFOs or in case of stop commanded by other parts of the program, this loops terminates and write its status in a Global Variable called "STOP". This Global Variable is implemented to stop the all program.

It is noteworthy that the channel control is read at each iteration of the loop, so it is possible to dynamically choose which channels to analyze.

The second main loop has a very similar task to the loop described above, with the difference of acting on the elements of the control queue. The Control FIFO contains information related to each PPS and, for each of these, 3 elements must be extracted.

The reason is related to the maximum size of the word transferable from the DMA. In fact, on FIFO hardware, it is not possible to enter data whose word length is higher than 64 bits. The data transmitted on the Control FIFO for each PPS are:

- Timestamp (64bit)
- Tick count of the last sample (32bit)
- Number of samples (U16)
- Valid Status of GPS signal (bool brought as I8)
- PPS Generation via Timeout (bool brought as I8)
- Tick count when PPS arrives.

This information is sent according to this configuration:

Figure 3.14: Control FIFO configuration

In the following figure, the implementation of second main loop is shown.

Figure 3.15: Second Main loop

Since the PPS arrives once a second, the speed with which the presence of the elements in the queue is controlled can be considerably lower than in the previous case. The rate of this loop is, in fact, 2Hz. Before the transfer in the new software queue, the PPS information from the Control FIFO are unbundled and inserted in a new cluster through a function. The subVI is shown below:

Figure 3.16: Unbundle Function for Elements of Control FIFO

The utilized GPS receiver is able to generate a PPS with an accuracy of 100 ns but the sampling resolution in terms of time, at 50 kHz is 20 μ s, so an error of PPS generation of 100 ns is negligible. For this reason the timestamp can be rounded to the closest entire second.

The third main loop is the heart of the program on the pc module. In this loop the data are taken from the software queues made in the previous loops and are processed. The data taken from the two queues allow us to implement the algorithm described in paragraph 3.2 but, as can be guessed from Figure 3.2, to analyze and process an observation window of duration 1s, there is the need to have both PPS that delimit it. It is therefore a program that works by comparing the i -th element to the $(i-1)$ -th element of the control queue. After defining the observation window and picking up the points belonging to this window, the actual processing takes place. Therefore, an estimate of the time instants corresponding to the acquired samples must be made, interpolation in the time domain and then a measurement of the synchrophasor using an algorithm that uses a frequency interpolation. The third main loop is presented in figure 3.15.

Figure 3.17: Third Main Loop

but also the presence of the GPS signal is guaranteed. The output of this VI is a cluster that contains these information about the observation window:

Figure 3.20: Output of Formulation VI

The calculations developed are:

$$deltatick = Tick Ts[i] - Tick Ts[i - 1] \quad (3.3)$$

$$desync\ new = Tick Ts - Tick\ last\ sample\ (element[i]) \quad (3.4)$$

$$desync\ old = Tick Ts - Tick\ last\ sample\ (element[i - 1]) \quad (3.5)$$

$$Nsample = Ns[i] - Ns[i - 1] \quad (3.6)$$

$$PPStick[i] - PPStick[i - 1] \quad (3.7)$$

$$= Nsample * tauc(tick) - desync\ old + (PPStick[i] - ticklastsample[i])$$

$$tauc(tick) = \frac{ticklastsample[i] + desynch\ old - PPStick[i - 1]}{Nsample} \quad (3.8)$$

$$tauc(tick) = \frac{ticklastsample[i] - ticklastsample[i - 1]}{Nsample} \quad (3.9)$$

$$tauc[s] = \frac{tauc(tick)}{deltatick} \quad (3.10)$$

Labview implementation of the “Samples between two PPS” is implemented in a Labview subVI called “Voltage and Current Elements” and it’s presented in Figure 3.19 .

Figure 3.21: Voltage and Current Elements subVI

This subVI has the simple task of eluding sufficient elements for the analysis time under consideration referring to the NSample obtained from the subVI "Formulation". An extra sample is taken for each channel because there is a need to have a point after the analysis window to get a correct interpolation on the first point. This necessity also justifies the presence of the "new data element" array. The nature of this necessity will be argued during the treatment of the time interpolation.

Before proceeding with the presentation of the data processing, it is opportune to introduce the concept of interpolation, specifically spline interpolation in the time domain. Moreover, referring to the doctoral thesis of Prof. Daniele Gallo entitled "PROCESSING OF ELECTRICAL SIGNALS FOR HARMONIC AND INTERHARMONIC ANALYSIS IN INDUSTRIAL MEASUREMENTS" [9] concepts of frequency analysis, spectral leakage, and interpolation in the frequency domain are recalled.

3.5 Interpolation in time domain

In the mathematical field of numerical analysis, interpolation is a method of constructing new data points within the range of a discrete set of known data points. In engineering and science, one often has a number of data points, obtained by sampling or experimentation, which represent the values of a function for a limited number of values of the independent variable. It is often required to interpolate (i.e., estimate) the value of that function for an intermediate value of the independent variable. A different problem which is closely related to interpolation is the approximation of a complicated function by a simple function. Suppose the formula for some given function is known, but too complex to evaluate efficiently. A few known data points from the original function can be used to create an interpolation based on a simpler function. When a simple function is used to estimate data points from the original, interpolation errors are usually present; however, depending on the problem domain and the interpolation method used, the gain in simplicity may be of greater value than the resultant loss in precision.

For example, suppose we have a table like this, which gives some values of an unknown function f .

Figure 3.22: Plot of the data points as given in the table.

Interpolation provides a means of estimating the function at intermediate points, such as $x=2.5$.

There are many different interpolation methods, some of which are described below. Some of the concerns to take into account when choosing an appropriate algorithm are: How accurate is the method? How expensive is it? How smooth is the interpolant? How many data points are needed?

One of the simplest methods is linear interpolation (sometimes known as lerp). Consider the above example of estimating $f(2.5)$. Since 2.5 is midway between 2 and 3, it is reasonable to take $f(2.5)$ midway between $f(2) = 0.9093$ and $f(3) = 0.1411$, which yields 0.5252.

Generally, linear interpolation takes two data points, say (x_a, y_a) and (x_b, y_b) , and the interpolant is given by:

$$y = y_a + \frac{(y_b - y_a)(x - x_a)}{x_b - x_a} \text{ at the point } (x, y)$$

This previous equation states that the slope of the new line between (x_a, y_a) and (x, y) is the same as the slope of the line between (x_a, y_a) and (x_b, y_b) . Linear interpolation is quick and easy, but it is not very precise. Another disadvantage is that the interpolant is not differentiable at the point x_k .

Figure 3.23: Plot of data with linear interpolation

The following error estimate shows that linear interpolation is not very precise. Denote the function which we want to interpolate by g , and suppose that x lies between x_a and x_b and that g is twice continuously differentiable. Then the linear interpolation error is:

$$|f(x) - g(x)| \leq C(x_b - x_a)^2 \text{ where } C = \frac{1}{8} \max_{r \in [x_a, x_b]} |g''(r)|$$

In words, the error is proportional to the square of the distance between the data points. The error in some other methods, including polynomial interpolation and spline interpolation (described below), is proportional to higher powers of the distance between the data points. These methods also produce smoother interpolants.

Polynomial interpolation is a generalization of linear interpolation. Note that the linear interpolant is a linear function. We now replace this interpolant with a polynomial of higher degree.

Consider again the problem given above. The following sixth degree polynomial goes through all the seven points:

$$f(x) = -0.0001521x^6 - 0.003130x^5 + 0.07321x^4 - 0.3577x^3 + 0.2255x^2 + 0.9038x$$

Substituting $x = 2.5$, we find that $f(2.5) = 0.5965$.

Generally, if we have n data points, there is exactly one polynomial of degree at most $n-1$ going through all the data points. The interpolation error is proportional to the distance between the data points to the power n . Furthermore, the interpolant is a polynomial and thus infinitely differentiable. So, we see that polynomial interpolation overcomes most of the problems of linear interpolation.

Figure 3.24: Plot of the data with polynomial interpolation applied

However, polynomial interpolation also has some disadvantages. Calculating the interpolating polynomial is computationally expensive compared to linear interpolation. Furthermore, polynomial interpolation may exhibit oscillatory artifacts, especially at the end points.

Polynomial interpolation can estimate local maxima and minima that are outside the range of the samples, unlike linear interpolation. For example, the interpolant above has a local maximum at $x \approx 1.566$, $f(x) \approx 1.003$ and a local minimum at $x \approx 4.708$, $f(x) \approx -1.003$. However, these maxima and minima may exceed the theoretical range of the function—for example, a function that is always positive may have an interpolant with negative values, and whose inverse therefore contains false vertical asymptotes.

More generally, the shape of the resulting curve, especially for very high or low values of the independent variable, may be contrary to commonsense, i.e. to what is known about the experimental system which has generated the data points. These disadvantages can be reduced by using spline interpolation or restricting attention to Chebyshev polynomials.

Remember that linear interpolation uses a linear function for each of intervals $[x_k, x_{k+1}]$. Spline interpolation uses low-degree polynomials in each of the intervals, and chooses the polynomial pieces such that they fit smoothly together. The resulting function is called a spline. For instance, the natural cubic spline is piecewise cubic and twice continuously differentiable.

Figure 3.25: Plot of the data with spline interpolation applied

Furthermore, its second derivative is zero at the end points.

The natural cubic spline interpolating the points in the table above is given by:

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} -0.1522x^3 + 0.9937x, & \text{if } x \in [0, 1], \\ -0.01258x^3 - 0.4189x^2 + 1.4126x - 0.1396, & \text{if } x \in [1, 2], \\ 0.1403x^3 - 1.3359x^2 + 3.2467x - 1.3623, & \text{if } x \in [2, 3], \\ 0.1579x^3 - 1.4945x^2 + 3.7225x - 1.8381, & \text{if } x \in [3, 4], \\ 0.05375x^3 - 0.2450x^2 - 1.2756x + 4.8259, & \text{if } x \in [4, 5], \\ -0.1871x^3 + 3.3673x^2 - 19.3370x + 34.9282, & \text{if } x \in [5, 6]. \end{cases}$$

In this case we get $f(2.5) = 0.5972$.

Like polynomial interpolation, spline interpolation incurs a smaller error than linear interpolation and the interpolant is smoother. However, the interpolant is easier to evaluate than the high-degree polynomials used in polynomial interpolation.

3.6 Discrete Fourier transform (DFT)

The spectrum of a discrete time sequence is a continuous complex value function of f and its calculation requires a continuous integral. In practical applications this calculation cannot be computed and the spectral analysis is performed through a different transformation called Discrete Fourier Transform (DFT) because the DFT of a finite sequence is performed analyzing only the values that are different from zero and the result is still a finite sequence. Moreover, for its calculation, very efficient algorithms were developed (FFT). Between DFT and FT there is a strong relationship,

in fact, the DFT components, $S(m)$, can be seen as L equally spaced samples of FT spectrum, that is:

$$S(m) = S(f) \Big|_{f=\frac{m}{LT_s}} = S(f) \Big|_{f=\frac{m}{T_w}} \quad m = 0, 1, \dots, L-1 \quad (3.11)$$

Where T_s is signal period and T_w is the Window period

This spectral sampling due to DFT is usually called picket fence effect, and it can produce misleading results, and only under opportune hypotheses, the DFT components can be utilized to obtain information about signals in frequency domain.

First of all, it is worthwhile noting that all the DFT components are taken only from positive frequency part of spectrum. But, because of the inherent periodicity of the spectrum after time sampling, the first half of these components (i.e. m from 0 to $L/2-1$) corresponds to the positive continuous frequency (i.e. f from 0 to $f_s/2$) and the second part (i.e. m from $L/2$ to $L-1$) correspond to the negative continuous frequency (i.e. f from 0 to $-f_s/2$).

Moreover, in order to obtain correct information about harmonic contents of the signal, the DFT spectral components should have always zero value with the only exception of the localization of the tone where they should give information about the presence of the tone. When this kind of situation applies, the spectral analysis is called synchronized and the DFT exactly picks up, at the same time, the main lobe peak and all the null points of side lobes (see Figure 3.24a). The relation that assures the synchronization of spectral samples with main lobe peak and side lobes point of zero can be easily deduced accounting the fact that when the relation

$$f_1 = k \frac{1}{T_w} \Rightarrow T_w = \frac{k}{f_1} = kT_1 \quad \forall k \geq 1 \quad (3.12)$$

holds this means that side lobes assume a value equal to zero each $1/T_w$ and also that the peak of the main lobe is located in one of the multiple of $1/T_w$. So, a spectrum sampled at these points will simply show all the information about the presence of tone (i.e. frequency, amplitude and phase angle) and, at the same time, hide the spectral leakage due to windowing (see Figure 3.24a).

Figure 3.26: Example of synchronized a) and desynchronized b) DFT analysis

On the contrary, adopting for spectral analysis a T'_w for which the relation (3.12) does not hold and this leads to a desynchronized analysis (see Figure 3.24b). In this case, the frequency locations of the main lobe peaks are between spectral samples obtained by DFT. So, none of the DFT spectral components have the exact information about amplitude, frequency and phase angle of the tone. It is worthwhile noting that with a desynchronized analysis the values of DFT spectral components are only due to spectral leakage and it is a big mistake to associate them to the presence of harmonic contents.

Anyway, the presence of a main lobe peak can be detected also after a desynchronized analysis, and it is possible to assume the maximum obtained spectral component as amplitude of the tone. It is useful to calculate, in this case, the maximum possible error in tone amplitude evaluation due to desynchronization. This parameter, of course, is dependent from the window adopted and it is called scallop loss, ΔA_{max} , and it is usually expressed in dB. A low value of scallop loss implies that the adopted window spectrum has a main lobe that is flat around the peak value. So the amplitude values,

even if they are obtained in slightly desynchronized situation, are close to the actual one.

Some brief recalls on the frequency domain interpolation technique are here summarized. A sampled and windowed single tone signal is considered:

$$s(k) = w(k) \cdot A_1 \cos\left(2\pi f_1 \frac{k}{f_s} + \varphi\right) \text{ with } k = 0, 1, \dots, L-1 \quad (3.13)$$

being A_1 the tone amplitude, f_1 the tone frequency, φ the phase angle and w a generic window of length $T_w = L/f_s$.

Thus, the signal spectrum evaluated by means of the DFT on L points and neglecting the negative frequency replica is:

$$S_L(m) = \frac{A \cdot \exp(j\varphi)}{2} \cdot W\left(\frac{m}{L} - \nu_1\right) \text{ with } m = 0, 1, \dots, L-1 \quad (3.14)$$

where $\nu_1 = f_1/f_s$ is the tone frequency normalized to the sampling frequency is introduced.

In presence of a small desynchronization between tone period and sampled time, none of the DFT components matches the actual tone frequency.

The actual signal normalized frequency is:

$$\nu_1 = \frac{M}{L} + \delta, \quad \text{with } -\frac{1}{2L} \leq \delta \leq \frac{1}{2L} \quad (3.15)$$

The actual amplitude, phase angle and frequency can be evaluated starting from the two DFT components nearest to the actual tone frequency by means of the relations:

$$\alpha = \frac{|S(M)|}{|S(M + \text{sign}(\delta))|} = \frac{|W(-\delta)|}{\left|W\left(\frac{1}{L} - \delta\right)\right|} = \alpha(\delta) \quad (3.16)$$

$$\alpha = \alpha(\delta) \Rightarrow \hat{\delta} = \delta(\alpha), \quad (3.17)$$

and then utilizing the relations

$$\hat{A}_1 = \frac{2|S(M)|}{|W(-\hat{\delta})|}, \quad \hat{\nu}_1 = \frac{M}{L} + \hat{\delta}, \quad \hat{\varphi} = \frac{\pi}{2} + \angle S(M) - \angle W(-\hat{\delta}). \quad (3.18)$$

The interpolation of a tone is based on the assumption of negligibility of the spectral leakage effects due to other tones. This can be obtained with the use of an opportune window []. Adopting the Hanning window, approximated expressions are:

$$|\hat{\delta}| = \frac{2 - \alpha}{1 + \alpha}, \quad \text{sign}(\hat{\delta}) = \text{sign}(|S(M+1)| - |S(M-1)|), \quad (3.19)$$

$$\hat{A}_1 = \pi |S(M)| \frac{\hat{\delta}(1 - \hat{\delta}^2)}{\sin(\pi \hat{\delta})}, \quad \hat{\varphi} = \frac{\pi}{2} + \angle S(M) - M \cdot \pi \cdot \hat{\delta}. \quad (3.20)$$

Figure 3.27: Example of the spectrum (--) and of DFT components (•) of a signal.

3.7 Data Processing function

After having clarified the importance of a synchronized analysis, the processing algorithm is presented on the samples belonging to a time interval between two PPSs.

As reported in paragraph 3.3, the generation of a PPS occurs in three modes: in the presence of the GPS signal, in the absence of the GPS signal and via TIMEOUT. The processing function implements all possible cases.

The following diagram shows the flow chart of the developed algorithm.

Figure 3.28: Flow chart of data processing function

The parameters of the observation window are chosen from the current and the last valid according to the validity of generation reported in the current parameters.

In order to have a greater clarity in the explanation of this function, it is necessary to analyze one case at a time and to see how the behavior of the function changes when the PPS generation mode changes. This is because, as reported by the flow chart in the Figure 3.26, preliminary operations are made according to the parameters entering this processing function in the previous iteration. Recall that only in the case where the generation occurs via TIMEOUT, it is considered not valid.

Suppose, in the first analysis, that the output of the subVI "Formulation" returns information related to a PPS generated with the presence of the GPS signal.

The Labview implementation as shown in figure 3.27.

In this case, the Boolean "Valid" is true therefore the "Control data" chosen is the current one. Suppose, furthermore, that the value of the "Residual" item leaving the case structure 1 is 0. In Case Structure 2 no element will be eliminated because the residual samples from previous iterations are absent. The available samples per second are given by the equation:

$$available\ data = Residue + Nsample \quad (3.21)$$

In order to obtain a correct interpolation in the time domain on the last point of the window, it is necessary to process $Nsample + 1$ points in order to guarantee continuity between two windows.

So when the condition:

$$available\ data > Nsample = True \quad (3.22)$$

the internal loop will execute the processing routine

Also in the current iteration, there is another loop that operates once for each channel and, assuming $Valid = True$, the case structure 4 passes the parameters of the observation window to the block for estimating the times of the real times.

The implementation of this block is as follows:

Figure 3.30: Labview implementation of the estimate of sampling time instant.

The offset is calculated by:

$$offset = tauc(tick) - \frac{desync[i - 1]}{deltatickout} \quad (3.23)$$

In the event that a sample coincides with the time when the pps interrupt occurs, although they are very small, the delays introduced by the traffic lights on the FPGA

may cause desync to be greater than T_{auc} . This event can not happen otherwise we would get a N_{sample} value larger than one unit. For this reason a coercion of desync has been made to the value of T_{auc} .

After completing the estimation of the actual sampling instants, it is possible to proceed with the interpolation function in the time domain. The VI Labview that implements the interpolation has 4 inputs and 2 outputs. The inputs are:

- the interpolation method
- the real elements of the Y axis
- the real elements of the X axis
- the elements of the X axis in which the interpolation is to be calculated.

The outputs are:

- The elements of the new Y axis
- The desired x axis elements.

Figure 3.29 shows the block diagram of the subVI.

Figure 3.31: Labview implementation of Interpolation function

The further operation that is performed in this function is the replacement of the last element calculated in the previous window with the first sample calculated for the current window. This iterative process allows to have no discontinuity and interpolation errors between the last point of the j -th window and the first of the window $(j + 1) - st$.

After performing this operation for each active channel, the value of N_{sample} in the shift register is set equal to 0. On the next iteration, this value is added to the residual and is compared with the number of points present between two PPSs. On this second iteration the available data value is less than N_{sample} and the function ends.

In the case where "Control data [i]" presents the Boolean $\text{Valid} = \text{False}$, the N_{sample} obtained from it is always the number of samples taken between two PPS, but this time the two PPS are not distant of 1s but of 41 million clock ticks. For this reason there will be samples made in excess of the analysis time of 1 s wanted. In this case, the last valid "Control Data" are used as control data. The calculation of the residual for the next iteration is:

$$\text{New Residue} = \text{available data} - \text{residual} - N_{\text{sample}} \text{ (of last valid)} \quad (3.24)$$

Unlike the previous case, the value of New Residue will not be null, so after a series of iterations, the condition will be verified again: $\text{available data} > N_{\text{sample}}$.

Obviously in this case, the PPS Timestamp is artificially constructed by adding 1 billion nanoseconds to the previous Timestamp and the new desync value is obtained from the equation:

$$\text{desynch new} = \text{desynch last} - N_{\text{sample}} * \text{tauc} + \text{deltatick}$$

Figure 3.32: Case structure with $\text{Valid} = \text{False}$

The last case that is considered is the case in which Control Data [i] has $\text{Valid} = \text{True}$, when for Control Data [i-1] $\text{Valid} = \text{False}$. In this condition it must be taken into account that the N_{sample} used in the previous observation windows may not

correspond to the real ones and therefore there may be points of the previous unprocessed windows. For this reason, the residual samples before this processing must be eliminated to return to synchronization conditions.

3.8 Measurements for Power Systems

This section describes the measurement function based on the IEEE Std C37.118.1™ -2011 standard entitled IEEE Standard for Synchrophasor Measurements for Power Systems[10]. Before proceeding to the software implementation, it is necessary to recall some fundamental concept on which the measurement algorithm is based.

Phasor: A complex equivalent of a sinusoidal wave quantity such that the complex modulus is the cosine wave amplitude, and the complex angle (in polar form) is the cosine wave phase angle.

Coordinated Universal Time (UTC): (Initials are ordered based on French language.) The time of day at the Earth's prime meridian (0° longitude). It is distributed by various media, including the Global Positioning System (GPS) system.

Synchronized phasor or synchrophasor: A phasor calculated from data samples using a standard time signal as the reference for the measurement.

Total Vector Error (TVE): The measure of error between the theoretical phasor value of the signal being measured and the phasor estimate.

Frequency error (FE): The measure of error between the theoretical frequency and the measured frequency for the given instant of time.

Rate of change of frequency (ROCOF) error (RFE): The measure of error between the theoretical ROCOF and the measured ROCOF for the given instant of time

Phasor representation of sinusoidal signals is commonly used in ac power system analysis. The sinusoidal waveform defined in Equation (3.25)

$$x(t) = X_m \cos(\omega t + \varphi) \quad (3.25)$$

is commonly represented as the phasor as shown in Equation (3.26):

$$\begin{aligned} X &= \left(\frac{X_m}{\sqrt{2}}\right) e^{j\varphi} \quad (3.26) \\ &= \frac{X_m}{\sqrt{2}} (\cos \varphi + j \sin \varphi) \\ &= X_r + jX_i \end{aligned}$$

where the magnitude is the root-mean-square (rms) value, $X_m/\sqrt{2}$, of the waveform, and the subscripts r and i signify real and imaginary parts of a complex value in rectangular components. The value of φ depends on the time scale, particularly where $t = 0$. It is important to note this phasor is defined for the angular frequency ω ; evaluation with other phasors must be done with the same time scale and frequency.

The synchrophasor representation of the signal $x(t)$ in Equation (3.25) is the value X in Equation (3.24) where φ is the instantaneous phase angle relative to a cosine function at the nominal system frequency synchronized to UTC. Under this definition, φ is the offset from a cosine function at the nominal system frequency synchronized to UTC. A cosine has a maximum at $t = 0$, so the synchrophasor angle is 0 degrees when the maximum of $x(t)$ occurs at the UTC second rollover (1 PPS time signal), and -90 degrees when the positive zero crossing occurs at the UTC second rollover (sin waveform). Figure 3.31 illustrates the phase angle/UTC time relationship.

Figure 3.33: Convention for synchrophasor representation

The sinusoid is shown in Equation (3.27):

$$x(t) = Xm \cos(\omega_0 t + \varphi) = Xm \cos(2\pi f_0 t + \varphi) \quad (3.27)$$

where f_0 is the nominal angular system frequency (50 Hz or 60 Hz) directly represented by the phasor in Equation (3.24). In the general case where the amplitude is a function of time $Xm(t)$ and the sinusoid frequency is also a function of time $f(t)$, we can define the function $g = f - f_0$ where f_0 is the nominal frequency and g is the difference between the actual and nominal frequencies (note that g will also be a function of time, e.g., $g(t) = f(t) - f_0$). The sinusoid can then be written as shown in Equation (3.28):

$$\begin{aligned} x(t) &= Xm(t) \cos(2\pi \int f dt + \varphi) \\ &= Xm(t) \cos(2\pi \int (f_0 + g) dt + \varphi) \\ &= Xm(t) \cos(2\pi f_0 t + (2\pi \int g dt + \varphi)) \end{aligned} \quad (3.28)$$

The synchrophasor representation for this waveform is shown in Equation (3.29):

$$X(t) = (Xm(t)/\sqrt{2})e^{j(2\pi \int g dt + \varphi)} \quad (3.29)$$

For the special case where $Xm(t) = Xm$ is constant and $g = \Delta f$ is a constant offset from the nominal frequency, $\int g(t) dt = \int \Delta f dt = \Delta f t$ so the synchrophasor is simply as shown in Equation (3.30):

$$X(t) = (Xm/\sqrt{2})e^{j(2\pi \Delta f t + \varphi)} \quad (3.30)$$

that will rotate at the uniform rate Δf , the difference between the actual and off-nominal frequency. This concept is illustrated in Figure 3.32. Consider that a sinusoid off-nominal system frequency is observed at intervals $\{0, T_0, 2T_0, 3T_0, \dots, nT_0, \dots\}$ where $T_0 = 1/f_0$ (the nominal power system period) and the corresponding phasor representations are $\{X_0, X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n, \dots\}$. If the sinusoid frequency $f \neq f_0$ and $f < 2f_0$, the observed phasor will have a constant magnitude, but the phase angles of the sequence of phasors $\{X_0, X_1, X_2, X_3, \dots, X_n, \dots\}$ will change uniformly at a rate $2\pi(f - f_0)T_0$, as illustrated. If these values were reported over time, they would continuously increase until they reached 180 degrees where they would wrap around to -180 degrees and continue to increase as shown in Figure 3.33 (synchrophasors are commonly reported in angles -180 degrees to +180 degrees rather than 0 to 360 degrees).

Figure 3.34: A sinusoid with a frequency $f > f_0$ is observed at instants that are T_0 seconds apart—the phase angle Φ increases uniformly in relation to the frequency difference, $f - f_0$

Figure 3.35: Sampling a power frequency sinusoid at off-nominal frequency

Several details of the synchrophasor definition shall be emphasized. All measurements are on a common time base and related to a common frequency, so the phase angle measurements are directly comparable. Differences in the actual frequency are included in the phase angle estimation. The synchrophasor estimate also includes the effects of all other signal contributions such as oscillations and local frequency swings. Synchrophasors are functions of time and will change from one value to the next unless the signal is a pure sinusoid at nominal system frequency. A precise time reference (clock) is required to provide the UTC time to determine the phase angle ϕ .

The theoretical values of a synchrophasor representation of a sinusoid and the values obtained from a PMU may include differences in both amplitude and phase. While they could be separately specified, the amplitude and phase differences are considered together in this standard in the quantity called total vector error (TVE). TVE is an expression of the difference between a “perfect” sample of a theoretical synchrophasor and the estimate given by the unit under test at the same instant of time. The value is normalized and expressed as per unit of the theoretical phasor. TVE is defined in Equation (3.31):

$$TVE(n) = \sqrt{\frac{(\widehat{X}_r(n) - X_r(n))^2 + (\widehat{X}_i(n) - X_i(n))^2}{(X_r(n))^2 + (X_i(n))^2}} \quad (3.31)$$

Where $\widehat{X}_r(n)$ and $\widehat{X}_i(n)$ are the sequences of estimates given by the unit under test, and $X_r(n)$ and $X_i(n)$ are the sequences of theoretical values of the input signal at the instants of time (n) assigned by the unit to those values. The values $X_r(n)$ and $X_i(n)$ can be determined in closed form in certain well-defined situations, such as constant frequency or phase offsets, and these situations are explored in this standard. Synchrophasor measurements shall be evaluated using the TVE criterion of Equation (3.31).

Synchrophasor, frequency, and ROCOF estimates shall be made so they can be reported at a constant rate, F_s , which is an integer number of times per second when the rate is greater than one per second, or an integer number of seconds between measurements when the measurement rate is equal to or slower than one per second. All three measurements shall be made and reported for the same reporting time. The reporting times shall be evenly spaced so the intervals between reports are all the same.

The PMU shall support data reporting (by recording or output) at sub-multiples of the nominal power-line (system) frequency. Required rates for 50 Hz and 60 Hz systems are listed in the table below:

System frequency	50 Hz			60 Hz					
Reporting rates (F_s —frames per second)	10	25	50	10	12	15	20	30	60

The actual rate to be used shall be user selectable. Support for other reporting rates is permissible, and including higher rates like 100/s or 120/s or rates lower than 10/s such as 1/s is encouraged. Note that rates lower than 10/s are not subject to the dynamic requirements of this standard. This means no filtering is required, so lower rate data ($< 10/s$) can be provided directly by selecting every n th sample from a higher rate stream. For a reporting rate N frames per second (fps) where N is a positive integer, the reporting times shall be evenly spaced through each second with frame number 0 (numbered 0 thru $N-1$) coincident with the UTC second rollover (e.g., coincident with a 1 PPS provided by GPS). These reporting times (time tags) are to be used for determining the instantaneous values of the synchrophasor as defined in 4.2. This is illustrated in Figure 2 where the reporting times are at 0, T_0 , $2T_0$, $3T_0$, $4T_0$, etc.

3.9 Labview software for Synchrophasors Measurement

As mentioned previously, the VI for measuring the synchrophasors is already implemented by LabView and is based on frequency interpolation. To adapt it to the developed system, it is sufficient to insert it into a For loop and supply it with the signal on which to apply the measurement. As can be seen from the Figure 3.35 there is also an algorithm for the compensation of systematic errors. The use of this latter function will be clarified below. The possibility for the user to change the reporting rate between 1Hz, 2Hz, 5Hz, 10Hz, 25Hz, and 50Hz has been implemented. The size of the measurement frame is decided by the user who has the possibility to choose an amplitude equal to at least the inverse of the reporting rate. With a wider frame of the inverse reporting rate, some measures will be taken between two seconds later, so we need to bring the second one next to the one we are analyzing into this function. For this reason the measurements are made in the second following the one that is being considered in the rest of the program.

Since a central unit for collecting data from this type of system has not yet been developed, the measurements are saved as text files on the Compact Rio hard disk. Furthermore, it is possible to save all the acquired samples for a subsequent offline analysis.

Figure 3.36: Labview implementation of measurement function

**CHAPTER 4: VALIDATION AND
VERIFICATION OF THE
PERFORMANCE OF THE
MEASUREMENT DEVICE**

4.1 Validation Test Performed

This chapter shows the tests performed to verify the performance of the developed measuring instrument. The features to be verified are:

- Synchronization between different devices
- Comparison between the spectrum of the resampled and non-resampled acquired signal
- Characterization of the system in order to compensate for systematic errors
- Reliability of the instrument

Synchronization between the various devices is essential for wide area monitoring. It is therefore necessary that all the meters correctly refer to the universal UTC time.

The second test verifies the functioning of the synchronization algorithm developed and shows the advantages of a synchronized sampling with respect to an unsynchronized sampling.

Like any measurement system, this device must also be characterized and possibly compensated for systematic errors. A compensation algorithm has therefore been developed which, depending on the frequency of the input signal, compensates systematic errors in module and phase. Therefore, tests were performed on all the Compact Rio before and after the compensation.

Finally, since this measuring device is set up for continuous monitoring of the activity on the network, a reliability test has been performed to evaluate the correct functioning of the instrument for long periods.

4.2 Verification of the synchronization with UTC

This qualitative test was developed to verify that the UTC obtained from the PPS generated on the various Compact Rio was the correct one. For realizing this test, a software was used in Labview that implements a programmed generation through the NI5422 generation module, having as reference the GPS signal by a GPS synchronization module, the NI6683H module. The VI is presented as follows:

Figure 4.1: Front Panel of software for checking UTC alignment

The signal generation was scheduled for 13: 41: 15,000 on 03/23/2018. The Voltage generated signal is a sinusoid with zero degree phase and 1.5V amplitude, 1.5V offset and 20Hz frequency. From the report of the Compact Rio on that date, the data obtained are:

TimeStamp	Frequency0	Amplitude0	Phase0	Phasor_real0	Phasor_imag0
134114.8	6480.859962	9.94319E-05	185.8978019	-9.89056E-05	-1.02171E-05
134115	20.00021124	1.059899352	0.06911698	1.059898581	0.001278576
134115.2	20.00006539	1.059876893	0.090529811	1.05987557	0.001674651

Figure 4.2: Compact Rio 9082 Report

TimeStamp	Frequency0	Amplitude0	Phase0	Phasor_real0	Phasor_imag0
134114.8	6480.871962	9.54646E-05	81.23093288	1.45538E-05	9.43487E-05
134115	20.00022124	1.059847989	0.045732558	1.059847651	0.000845953
134115.2	20.00007739	1.059913357	0.066640129	1.05991264	0.001232774

Figure 4.3: Compact Rio 9039a Report

TimeStamp	Frequency0	Amplitude0	Phase0	Phasor_real0	Phasor_imag0
134114.8	6934.998285	0.000103721	323.2247434	8.30796E-05	-6.20956E-05
134115	20.0000187	1.059845424	0.085597814	1.059844241	0.00158337
134115.2	20.00025144	1.059932206	0.091618486	1.059930851	0.001694878

Figure 4.4: Compact Rio 9034b Report

From the results obtained it is possible to ascertain that the acquisition assumes different values different from the noise from the correct moment on all the Compact Rio.

4.3 The efficacy of resampling

This test is performed to verify the efficacy of the synchronized resampling by comparing the interpolated signal spectrum with the non-interpolated signal spectrum. For the realization of this test, the points of the interpolated waveform and of the non-interpolated waveform have been memorized in a generic second. The input signal generation is entrusted to the 6135A / PMU CAL calibrator which is able to generate a three-phase voltage and a phase 0 (cosine) in the steady state at the instant of generation of a PPS. The generated signal is a voltage signal of amplitude 10V, phase 0 degrees and frequency 50Hz. Through a VI not contained on the Compact Rio, in post processing, a DFT was performed and the spectra of the signals with and without interpolation are compared. The results of the processing are shown in the figure 4.5:

Figure 4.5: DFT of Module

This figure confirms what was said previously about the importance of synchronizing an observation window for measurement through a DFT. As seen theoretically in figure 3.26, having a synchronized sampling allows to obtain more accurate measurements thanks to a lower spectral dispersion.

4.4 Performance verification

The following test was achieved for performance verification and systematic error compensation.

The input signal generation is entrusted to the 6135A / PMU CAL calibrator which is able to generate a three-phase voltage and a phase 0 (cosine) phase in the steady state at the instant of generation of a PPS. Given the high accuracy of the generation of this instrument, it is possible to assume that the generation uncertainty is negligible compared to the acquisition uncertainty.

Figure 4.6: Measurement Setup for Characterization of CRIOs

In the first analysis, amplitude error, phase error, frequency error and TVE are evaluated according to regulation [10] in range [45-55] Hz. The magnitude error, the phase error and frequency error are obtained as follows:

$$\varepsilon\% = \left(\frac{A_{acq}}{A_{gen}} - 1 \right) * 100 \quad (4.1) \quad \Delta\varphi = \varphi_{acq} - \varphi_{gen} \quad (4.2)$$

$$FE = f_{acq} - f_{gen} \quad (4.3)$$

the TVE formula is invoked in (3.29).

Having a text file containing the generation data provided by PMUCAL, it is possible to compare these data with those acquired by the Compact Rio. The goal is to characterize the system in frequency by measuring the magnitude errors and the phase errors for each channel for correcting the systematic errors dynamically.

For the sake of brevity, the amplitude, phase, frequency and TVE errors are reported on an XY graph in which linearly equispaced fundamental frequencies of generated signals are placed on the X axis and the errors for the three-phase voltage or the three-phase current on the Y axis. For each frequency the maximum error analyzed is reported on 20 seconds with a Reporting Rate of 5Hz (101 measurements).

Figure 4.7: Voltage Magnitude Error 9082

Figure 4.8: Current Magnitude Error 9082

Figure 4.9: Voltage Phase Error 9082

Figure 4.10: Current Phase Error 9082

Figure 4.11: Voltage Frequency Error 9082

Figure 4.12: Current Frequency Error 9082

Figure 4.13: Voltage TVE 9082

Figure 4.14: Current TVE 9082

Figure 4.15: Voltage Magnitude Error 9034 a

Figure 4.16: Current Magnitude Error 9034 a

Figure 4.17: Voltage Phase Error 9034 a

Figure 4.18: Current Phase Error 9034 a

Figure 4.19: Voltage Frequency Error 9034 a

Figure 4.20: Voltage Frequency Error 9034 a

Figure 4.21: Voltage TVE 9034 a

Figure 4.22: Current TVE 9034 a

Figure 4.23: Voltage Magnitude Error 9034 b

Figure 4.24: Current Magnitude Error 9034 b

Figure 4.25: Voltage Phase Error 9034 b

Figure 4.26: Current Phase Error 9034 b

Figure 4.27: Voltage Frequency Error 9034 b

Figure 4.28: Current Frequency Error 9034 b

Figure 4.29: Voltage TVE 9034 b

Figure 4.30: Current TVE 9034 b

What is noticed from these results is a phase delay of almost a period that decreases with increasing frequency. This is the classic behavior of a constant delay (about 19.194 m°). One of the future goals of this thesis is trace the cause of this systematic delay.

Through this Labview software, we obtain the coefficients of the interpolating polynomials for the phase and amplitude error compensation. This software generates two text files that are copied to the Compact Rio and allow real-time compensation of the measurements performed. By measuring the frequency of the input signal, it is possible to use the coefficients of the interpolating polynomial for the phase and for the amplitude for calculating the value of the phase error and the amplitude error. In order to obtain the compensated measurements, the value of amplitude polynomial, calculated at measured frequency, must be multiplied for the measured amplitude and the value of phase polynomial, calculated in the same frequency, must be subtracted to measured one. These elaborations derive from definitions (4.1) and (4.2)

After compensation, Magnitude Errors and Phase Errors Frequency Errors and TVEs become as in following pages.

Figure 4.31: Voltage Magnitude Error 9082

Figure 4.32: Current Magnitude Error 9082

Figure 4.33: Voltage Phase Error 9082

Figure 4.34: Current Phase Error 9082

Figure 4.35: Voltage Frequency Error 9082

Figure 4.36: Current Frequency Error 9082

Figure 4.37: Voltage TVE 9082

Figure 4.38: Current TVE 9082

Figure 4.39: Voltage Magnitude 9034 a

Figure 4.40: Current Magnitude 9034 a

Figure 4.41: Voltage Phase Error 9034 a

Figure 4.42: Current Phase Error 9034 a

Figure 4.43: Voltage Frequency Error 9034 a

Figure 4.44: Current Frequency Error 9034 a

Figure 4.45: Voltage TVE 9034 a

Figure 4.46: Current TVE 9034 a

Figure 4.47: Voltage Magnitude Error 9034 b

Figure 4.48: Current Magnitude Error 9034 b

Figure 4.49: Voltage Phase Error 9034 b

Figure 4.50: Current Phase Error 9034 b

Figure 4.51: Voltage Frequency Error 9034 b

Figure 4.52: Current Frequency Error 9034 b

Figure 4.53: Voltage TVE 9034 b

Figure 4.54: Current TVE 9034 b

The results show the significant effect of compensation in terms of angle errors and TVE. In fact, phase error goes from about 345° to a maximum, after compensation, of 10m° . The TVE goes from about 28% to a maximum value of about 0.046% after compensation.

4.5 Verification of the reliability of the system

The measurement device presented in this thesis work is developed for a continuous monitoring of the railway network activity. In order to guarantee that the compensated is done properly, the measurement device has been subjected to a test of about 6 hours in which particular attention is paid to the module and the phase of the acquired signal over time. For realizing this test, a software was used in Labview that implements a programmed generation through the NI5422 generation module, having as reference the GPS signal by a GPS synchronization module, the NI6683H module. The generated signal is a voltage signal of 10V peak, frequency of 48 Hz and an initial phase of 0 degrees.

The following waveform graph is the amplitude value per second. On the same image, the mean value and standard deviation is shown.

Figure 4.55: Amplitude Voltage in Reliability analysis

The trend of the phase is as follow:

Figure 4.56: Phase Voltage in Reliability analysis

Conclusions

The objectives set for this thesis work required the development of a measuring device able to acquire to analyze signals coming from railway substations or trains. The measurement system presented, stand alone, is able to acquire signals with a sampling frequency up to 50kHz, a frequency that allows the analysis of the dynamic effects and high frequency phenomena of the railway system.

Moreover, the acquisition system performs synchronized measurements in absolute time instants and, thanks to this feature, it is possible to monitor the network status at different locations. Thanks to the CompactRio PC module, it is possible to easily implement new algorithms for energy measurement and Power Quality measurements.

The results of the performed measurement verify the high accuracy of the system and the goodness of the synchronization, making the system comparable to a PMU.

A starting point in the research that offers this thesis work is find a way to use the measurements obtained on this system to monitor the status of the network, sending them to a Central unit.

Vanvitelli University has the task of develop suitable communications architecture and central data collection system to allow data transfer from digitizers placed on board trains and in substations. All data are provided with proper time stamp in order to correlate different event.

Refecences

- [1] COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 1301/2014 of 18 November 2014 on the technical specifications for interoperability relating to the ‘energy’ subsystem of the rail system in the Union
- [2] COMMISSION REGULATION (EU) No 1302/2014 of 18 November 2014 concerning a technical specification for interoperability relating to the ‘rolling stock — locomotives and passenger rolling stock’ subsystem of the rail system in the European Union
- [3] EN 50463-2 – Railway Applications - Energy measurement on board trains - Part 2: Energy measuring
- [4] EN 50163 - Railway applications - Supply voltages of traction systems, 2006.
- [5] EN 50388 – Railway Applications - Power supply and rolling stock - Technical criteria for the coordination between power supply (substation) and rolling stock to achieve interoperability, 2012-08.
- [6] CLC/TR50646 Railway applications – Fixed Installations – Specifications for reversible direct current substations
- [7] Domínguez, M., Fernández-Cardador, A., Cucala, A.P., Pecharromán, R.R., 2012. Energy savings in metropolitan railway substations through regenerative energy recovery and optimal design of ATO speed profiles. IEEE Trans. Autom. Sci. Eng. 9, 496 –504. doi:10.1109/TASE.2012.2201148
- [8] Faktenblatt Programm Elektrizität 31 «Zug um Zug mehr Effizienz», Swiss Federal Office of Energy SFOE, http://www.bfe.admin.ch/php/modules/publikationen/stream.php?extlang=de&name=de_290519393.pdf
- [9] "PROCESSING OF ELECTRICAL SIGNALS FOR HARMONIC AND INTERHARMONIC ANALYSIS IN INDUSTRIAL MEASUREMENTS", Tesi di Dottorato di Ricerca in Conversione dell’Energia Elettrica, Prof. Daniele Gallo

[10] IEEE Standard for Synchrophasor Measurements for Power Systems Sponsored by the Power System Relaying Committee 28 December 2011 IEEE Power & Energy Society IEEE Std C37.118.1™-2011

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